

**Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with
Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive
Gender Equality Plans**

D3.2 Report on the implementation of the capacity building scheme

South-East European Research Centre (SEERC)

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List of Acronyms

ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
M&Ms	Mentoring and Monitoring Meetings
IOs	Implementing Organisations
T	Task
WP	Work Package
4I-GEPs	Innovative, Intersectional, Inclusive and Impactful Gender Equality Plans

The SUPPORTER project

SUPPORTER, “SecUring sPORTs Education thRough innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans”, is an EU-funded project running from April 2023 until September 2025. Launched on 19 April 2023, it aims to support eight sports higher education institutions from Central and Eastern Europe in developing their own intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful Gender Equality Plans which explicitly address gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

Through mutual learning and interactive exchanges, the project will seek to:

1. Identify and document systemic challenges faced by sports higher education institutions in advancing gender equality and eradicating gender-based violence.
2. Develop activities tailored to each partner institution.
3. Strengthen the sports institutions’ organisational capacity to address gender equality with an intersectional approach.
4. Foster an inclusive institutional culture by developing mutual-learning processes.
5. Strengthen networking and exchange among sports institutions and with communities of practice
6. Foster gender-related institutional, sustainable, transformative changes in the sports institutions with a specific attention on the challenge of gender-based violence -thus ultimately fostering the institutions and their Gender Equality Plans’ inclusiveness and the overall adherence to intersectionality.

While initially partnering with eight institutions, the SUPPORTER project aspires to target and reach the wider sports ecosystem and its various organisations in Central and Eastern Europe and beyond, and in the long run contribute to wide societal changes.

Project Partners

<p>SCIENCE CONNECT YOUR PARTNER IN SCIENCE</p>	European Science Foundation (ESF)
<p>UNIVERSITY OF GOTHENBURG</p>	Göteborgs Universitet (UGOT), Sweden
<p>SOUTH-EAST EUROPEAN RESEARCH CENTRE</p>	Kentro Erevnon Notioanatolikis Evropis Astiki mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia, The South-East European Research Centre (SEERC), Greece
<p>УНИВЕРЗИТЕТ У БАЊОЈ ЛУЦИ UNIVERSITY OF BANJA LUKA</p>	Univerzitet u Banjoj Luci (UNIBL), Bosnia & Herzegovina
<p>University of Ljubljana Faculty of Sport</p>	Univerza v Ljubljani (UL), Slovenia
<p>UNIVERZITA KARLOVA</p>	Univerzita Karlova (CU), Czechia
<p>НАЦИОНАЛНА СПОРТНА АКАДЕМИЈА "ВАСИЛ ЛЕВСКИ" БЪЛГАРИЯ</p>	Natsionalna Sportna Akademiya Vassil Levski (NSA), Bulgaria
<p>LIETUVOS SPORTO UNIVERSITETAS</p>	Lietuvos Sporto Universitetas (LSU), Lithuania
<p>Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara</p>	Universitatea de Vest din Timisoara (UVT), Romania
	Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport (GSTUPES), Georgia
	Universitatea de Stat de Educație Fizică și Sport (USEFS), Moldova

Summary

This deliverable delineates the capacity building scheme of the SUPPORTER project and the steps taken for its successful implementation and completion. This comprehensive and dynamic plan has been strategically designed to equip eight Implementing Organisations (IOs) in Central and Eastern European higher education sports institutions with crucial knowledge and skills for advancing gender+ equality and played a pivotal role in the successful development of their innovative, intersectional, inclusive and impactful Gender Equality Plans (4I-GEPs).

The deliverable outlines the three core capacity building activities: the training programme, the mutual learning programme, and the mentoring and monitoring scheme. The training programme offered IOs the necessary theoretical knowledge and practical skills for the co-design and implementation of their institutional roadmaps towards gender+ equality and 4I-GEPs. The mutual learning programme expanded on the learnings of the training programme, facilitated the exchange of ideas and best practices among participants, and fostered collaboration, while the mentoring and monitoring scheme oversaw the co-creation and implementation of institutional roadmaps and 4I-GEPs offering invaluable support and tailored guidance to the eight IOs. The deliverable also provides a detailed description of each activity's content and objectives, and crucial information about participant feedback and organisers' reflections.

Highlights

- The capacity building scheme is a **comprehensive and dynamic pathway** comprising three interrelated and complementary activities: training, mutual learning, and mentoring and monitoring.
- The activities offered **valuable guidance, feedback and support** to implementing organisations during the co-design and implementation processes of their **institutional roadmaps** and the development of their **innovative, intersectional, inclusive and impactful Gender Equality Plans**.
- The **training programme** equipped implementing organisations with the necessary skills and knowledge on a wide range of **gender+ equality topics**, from fundamental concepts to more complex themes.
- The **mutual learning programme** through a series of workshops and sessions, bilateral meetings and learning diaries helped implementing organisations to **consolidate their learnings, exchange ideas and best practices, and reflect on their experiences**.
- The **mentoring and monitoring scheme** supported IOs during the co-design and implementation of institutional roadmaps and the development of 4I-GEPs, **providing constructive feedback and a safe environment for self-reflection and self-evaluation**.

Introduction

The SUPPORTER capacity building scheme is a **dynamic and evolving pathway** designed to empower eight Implementing Organisations (IOs) in Central and Eastern European sports institutions (universities/faculties) with the essential knowledge and skills for advancing gender+ equality. This comprehensive scheme involves three types of activities: **a training programme, a mutual learning programme, and a mentoring and monitoring scheme.**

In its entirety, the horizontal capacity building scheme is central to the SUPPORTER methodology (see Vilarchao et al., 2024) that includes three interconnected and complementary processes. Firstly, **the analytical process**, which was completed under WP2, involved the mapping of the theoretical background (Strid et al., 2023) and the available tools and materials (Grahn et al., 2023) upon which the training programme was based. Subsequently, during **the reflective process** IOs completed a self-assessment exercise which significantly informed the design, objectives and learning outcomes of the SUPPORTER capacity building scheme. Moreover, the reflective process that continued throughout the roadmap co-creation and implementation was strongly supported by the training programme, the mutual learning programme and the mentoring and monitoring scheme, all of which were continuously adapted to ensure that the needs of different institutions were effectively addressed.

Finally, **the implementation process** involved the co-design and implementation of the institutional roadmaps and the development of new intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful gender equality plans (4I-GEPs) aiming to foster inclusive gender+ equality and generate institutional changes in the eight universities/faculties. Each of the roadmaps consists of several Grounding Actions which formed the basis for the new 4I-GEPs. Additionally, the implementation process has produced a wide range of outputs, including a compilation of lessons learned, SUPPORTER guidelines and recommendations, and policy briefs. This process was further informed and refined through the feedback collected from the capacity building activities.

The current deliverable examines the work undertaken under WP3, mostly by the core team, for the successful implementation and completion of the SUPPORTER capacity building scheme.

1. Capacity Building Scheme

As previously mentioned, the horizontal capacity building scheme, which was designed and delivered under WP3, consists of **three interrelated and complementary components: the training programme, the mutual learning programme, and the mentoring and monitoring scheme.** Through its training and mutual learning parts, the scheme aimed to equip the implementing organisations with practice-driven knowledge, which was deemed crucial for the successful implementation of institutional changes pertaining to gender equality in the context of sports education. The mentoring and monitoring programme offered guidance and support to IOs during the challenging phases of co-designing, updating and implementing their institutional roadmaps towards gender+ equality and by extension their 4I-GEPs.

The capacity building scheme was developed on three main principles: **adaptability and flexibility, continuous assessment and feedback, and anticipation.** The first principle showcases the evolving nature of the scheme, which was not cast in stone, but constantly adapting according to the needs and obstacles encountered during the different project activities. The second principle refers to the collection of data and feedback at different points throughout the

project to facilitate the planning of the next cycle of activities. Finally, the last principle, anticipation, involves designing activities based on the explicit or implicit assessment of IOs' needs (i.e. either asking the IOs directly about their training needs or inferring such information from the institutional mappings).

The three core activity types of the capacity building scheme, namely **training**, **mutual learning**, and **mentoring and monitoring**, follow the aforementioned principles in order to cater for the different capacity-building needs of IOs, and ensure the successful and effective implementation of institutional roadmaps (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Capacity building scheme cycle

The capacity building scheme was informed by the results of the three mapping activities conducted in WP2. These activities included a) the mapping of the state of the art of gender+ equality and gender-based violence policies in sport education, b) the mapping of existing trainings by other EU-funded projects on gender equality and gender-based violence, and c) the mapping of the IOs' institutional context including an analysis of their pre-SUPPORTER organisational GEPs based on a self-assessment exercise. As a result, the horizontal capacity building scheme was able to provide not only practical knowledge and skills to IOs, but a tailored learning experience based on their individual context.

The training programme included three modules, each one consisting of three sessions totalling nine sessions. It addressed a diverse range of gender+ equality topics, starting with introductory concepts such as gender and gender equality in the EU, and gradually advancing to more complex themes such as systemic gender-based violence and intersectionality.

The mutual learning programme aimed at consolidating the learnings of the training programme and facilitating the exchange of best practices and know-how among IOs. It consisted of three in-person mutual learning workshops, five online mutual learning sessions, two rounds of bilateral meetings among IOs, and seven learning diaries.

Lastly, the mentoring and monitoring scheme actively supported the co-design and implementation of institutional roadmaps, enabling self-reflection and providing IOs with constructive feedback and guidance through eight Mentoring and Monitoring meetings (M&Ms) held between IOs and the core team.

2. Training Programme

The SUPPORTER training programme is one of three components of the SUPPORTER capacity building scheme consisting of three modules of three sessions each. The modules incrementally increased in complexity and drew on the feedback from previous trainings, the mutual learning activities, Learning Diary 1 and the M&Ms. Moreover, each module fed into the subsequent mutual learning activities and trainings to ensure that the scheme met the actual needs of the consortium IOs.

The development of the SUPPORTER training programme (T3.1) is based on the SUPPORTER analytical process, which involved the mapping activities mentioned in the previous section that contributed to identifying knowledge and providing profound insights crucial for the project's implementation. The training programme was designed to provide systematic training to incrementally enhance the theoretical and practical knowledge of institutional actors to enable the co-creation and implementation of intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful GEPs tailored to sports higher education institutions, explicitly addressing gender-based violence.

The programme was developed in three modules, each including three half-day, or even longer, sessions on the following topics: 1) basic training on institutional change (incl. impact assessment and governance), gender equality and GEPs; 2) inclusive and progressive GEPs; and 3) gender-based violence. Theoretically, the logic of the training programme is based on long-term thinking, sustainability, and progressiveness as the overarching themes in the programme. Hence, the mutual learning programme, comprising a set of systematic activities evolving throughout the entire project lifespan, facilitated the consolidation of insights and experiences gained throughout the training programme (T3.2), the co-design and implementation of the institutional roadmaps (T4.1 and T4.2), and the exchange of related thoughts, considerations and experiences among the consortium IOs. Practically, the logic of the training programme follows the six main steps of a GEP ([EIGE's GEAR tool](#)), with each module addressing the knowledge and practice needed to design and implement each step of a 4I-GEP:

- 1) Getting started: Getting inspiration.
- 2) Gender Analysis: Analysing and assessing the status of gender equality in the organisation.
- 3) Setting up the GEP: Identification of objectives, setting targets and measures to remedy the identified problems, allocating resources and responsibilities, and defining timelines.
- 4) Implementation: Implementing the planned activities and enlarging the stakeholders' network.
- 5) Monitoring & evaluation: Assessment of the implementation process and the progress achieved against the aims and objectives identified in the GEP.
- 6) What next?: Development of the next GEP building on experiences, learnings and achievements, while ensuring the sustainability of these actions.

Figure 2 – GEP design cycle

2.1 Training Modules and Sessions

The training programme addressed the theory and practice, and knowledge and skills needed to set up and implement a 4I-GEP. Also, as previously described, it was structured to address each of the six main steps of a GEP.

More specifically, the first module offered basic training on the following key concepts: institutional change, gender equality and GEPs, addressing the first step of a GEP: *Getting started, getting inspiration*.

The second module was an intermediate training on gender equality and inclusive and progressive GEPs, addressing the second and third steps of a GEP: *Analysing and assessing the status quo in the organisation*, and *Setting up a gender equality plan, identification of objectives, setting targets and measures to remedy the identified problems, allocating resources and responsibilities, and defining timelines*, and *Exploring the 4Is and their operationalisation for the sport context*.

The third module was an advanced training on gender equality in sports higher education and research institutions, including 4I-GEPs, addressing the fourth, fifth and sixth steps of a GEP: *Implementation: implementing the planned activities and enlarging the stakeholders' network*, *Monitoring & evaluation: assessment of the implementation process and the progress achieved against the aims and objectives identified in the GEP*, and *What next?: development of the next GEP building on experiences, learnings and achievements, while ensuring the sustainability of these actions*.

Out of the nine training sessions, one was held offline, while the remaining eight were offered online. The trainings were delivered by consortium experts or invited external expert trainers and followed a structured script (see Annex 1).

All sessions started with a clear introduction and warm-up exercise, followed by the presentation of the theoretical element underpinning the focus of the session. The theoretical part was in turn followed by practical group exercises on themes related to the topic. Group work among IOs was

facilitated by a core team member who offered guidance and helped them navigate the exercise. Each group also consisted of a note taker and a rapporteur, while the trainer visited all groups to support the exercise and help advance the discussion. The results of the group work were shared in plenary by the group rapporteurs and discussed among the IOs to facilitate mutual learning. Each session ended with a feedback questionnaire, the learnings from which were used to improve the following training sessions. To consolidate the lessons from the training modules, exchange related good practices, share questions and overall experiences, the completion of each training module was accompanied by the organisation of a mutual learning workshop and other mutual learning sessions. Moreover, during the M&Ms the core team together with the IOs assessed the concrete application of the learnings into their roadmap design and implementation, and also the needs for further training on specific topics.

The next sections provide an overview of the Training Modules' content. For further details on the learning objectives of the module and the content of each session see Annex 1.

2.1.1 Training Module I: Basic training on key concepts, institutional change, gender equality, gender-based violence and GEPs

This first of three modules offered a basic training to ensure a shared understanding of key concepts and contexts. Over three sessions, it addressed:

- Key concepts, e.g., gender, gender+, intersectionality, gender-based violence
- Main issues at stake regarding gender equality in research and higher education in the context of sport
- Prevalence and consequences of gender-based violence in the European Research Area
- Policies on gender equality and gender-based violence in the European Research Area
- Gender equality plans as the main instrument towards institutional change. Introduction to the six steps of a GEP. Importance of stakeholder mapping?
- Learn about prerequisites and key success factors of institutional change processes.
- Gain awareness about how to facilitate change and how to deal with resistances.

This module was composed of the following sessions:

- Session 1: Key concepts and shared understanding.
- Session 2: Institutional change.
- Session 3: Gender equality plans.

2.1.2 Training Module II: Intermediate training on gender equality and inclusive and progressive GEPs

The second module turned the focus to the sports environment and the specifics in the context of sport higher education and research. It addressed the second and third steps of the gender equality plan, including analysing and assessing the state of play in the institution to provide insights on which measures need to be implemented, and setting up a 4I-GEP. It used the impact drivers to support transformative aspects of the IOs gender equality plans, including core team of change agents, capacity/skills of the change agents for driving institutional change; leadership actively committed; availability of resources; data collection and statistical analysis; involvement of internal stakeholders, involvement of external stakeholders and experts; coverage of the different

dimensions/areas of gender equality institutional change; transparency and accountability; institutional policy making based on a robust understanding of gender equality; organisational culture; and organisational governance. Session 1 and 2 were organised with the support of the sister projects Agrigep and GenderSAFE. A member of the advisory board intervened in session 3.

This module was composed of the following sessions:

- Session 1: Analysis and assessment of the state of play in the institution: data collection and data analysis; focus on sport higher education institutions – focus on data.
- Session 2: Analysis and assessment of the state of play in the institution: measures, policy and legislation; focus on sport higher education institutions – focus on policy and measures.
- Session 3: Setting up a gender equality plan; focus on sport higher education institutions.

2.1.3 Training Module III: Advanced training on gender+ equality and 4I-GEPs

This third and final module offered advanced training on gender+ equality and 4I-GEPs in the sports environment. It built on the first two modules of training and mutual learning, and the work carried out by the IOs in T2.1 and T2.3. The training focused on the fourth, fifth and sixth steps of the gender equality plan, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and what happens after the gender equality plan. It reviewed key concepts and revisited the overall meaning of intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful GEPs by discussing the theory and providing examples from the ‘model institution’ and other organisations.

This module was composed of the following sessions:

- Session 1: Implementing a gender equality plan (step 4).
- Session 2: Monitoring progress and evaluating a gender equality plan (step 5).
- Session 3: What comes after the gender equality plan (step 6).

2.2 Timeline

The table below provides information about the timeline, content, format and number participants of the training programme.

Topic		Format	Month/Date	Number of participants
Training Module I				
Training Session I	Key concepts and a shared understanding	Online	M9, September 2023	29
Training Session II	Institutional change	Online	M9, September 2023	34
Training Session III	Gender equality plans, six steps	Offline (Strasbourg)	M9, September 2023	33

Training Module II				
Training Session I	Gender analysis and assessment: data and indicators	Online	M13, April 2024	43
Training Session II	Gender analysis and assessment: policy	Online	M13, April 2024	31
Training Session III	Setting up a GEP including gender-based violence	Online	M14, May 2024	43
Training Module III				
Training Session I	Implementation of a GEP in the sport's field	Online	M21, January 2025	32
Training Session II	Monitoring and evaluation: methods for 4I GEP	Online	M22, February 2025	25
Training Session III	Post-GEP, what comes next? Sustainability	Online	M22, February 2025	19

2.3 Feedback from Participants

After the end of each training module, participants completed an online survey including both numerical and open-ended feedback. More specifically, attendees were asked to rate certain aspects of the session such as tempo, structure, and usefulness of content among others on a scale of 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest) as well as provide individual comments.

Overall, participant feedback has been very positive with the average for all modules being 4.4. Attendees were very satisfied with the tempo, structure, usefulness and learning outcomes of all sessions as well as with the trainers' knowledge, communication skills and support/advice offered. In fact, the training across all modules met or exceeded participant expectations in most areas. The consistently strong ratings for trainer performance, structure, and usefulness demonstrate that the sessions were well-designed and effectively delivered. Session 2 of module 2 (Gender analysis and assessment: policy) received the highest score (4.72), showing that the contribution of Agrigep was particularly interesting (GEP in CEEs in another field).

Regarding open-ended feedback, after the first session participants requested longer breaks and more opportunities for discussions with the facilitator, which was taken into account for the following session. Moreover, an exercise was organised in the session held in Strasbourg to allow participants to get to know each other since this was the only time they met face-to-face. Attendees found session 2 of module 2 very well planned, particularly in relation to group work, although they requested a little more time. They were also very satisfied with the trainer whom they described as excellent and motivational. While participants appreciated the balance between theory and practice in session 3 of module 2, they reported some difficulties with Miro. The platform had been employed as a practical tool facilitating the collaboration of cross-functional teams with comprehensive training provided at the beginning of the project. However, since participants found its interface

difficult to navigate, it was replaced in following sessions. Lastly, attendees valued the group discussions during all sessions of module 3 and found the content very informative.

2.4 Self-assessment by Organisers

The objectives of the training programme were largely achieved in providing the necessary basic knowledge that IOs needed to develop and implement their Grounding Actions. The three modules assisted IOs to develop their capacity to assess their own state of play, share common understanding and knowledge, support the development of their own GEP, and foster self-reflection as well as inspiration from others through mutual learning and exchanges. Moreover, the training scheme contributed to establishing a sense of community among all the IOs.

To achieve these objectives, the trainings were organised with theoretical and practical sessions in subgroups. In general, the introductory lectures of each session were delivered by an academic expert in the field, and therefore set the theoretical and conceptual basis for the session, while also enabling participants to reflect on their practical experiences of the topic. The exercises that followed were designed to allow participants, divided into subgroups, to reflect on the topic of the session and share their own practices. This structure was well appreciated, and the invited speakers (internal or external) were regarded as knowledgeable trainers who provided useful advice and support.

The timing of the sessions was adapted following participant feedback, in particular by including longer breaks and allowing more time for group work, as well as by starting sessions earlier due to time differences. Moreover, Miro was replaced by other tools, as some participants found it difficult to use.

Reflecting on the organisation of the training, which was conducted almost entirely online except for one session, it would have been beneficial to start with the planned face-to-face training. This would have allowed more interaction from the outset among the IOs' participants. Indeed, there was better engagement in group work during Modules II and III.

The most challenging aspect in planning and delivering these sessions was the varying levels of participants' prior knowledge. This required offering some more basic sessions or units alongside more advanced ones.

For the subgroup work, we tried to alternate between groups with participants of similar levels of knowledge and mixed groups combining more and less advanced IOs. The question remains whether it is preferable to have more homogeneous groups. However, it is clear that having more advanced IOs working together with less experienced ones contributed to the overall outcome of all IOs advancing in their policy implementation and adopting a new GEP.

Another difficulty concerned the integration of the 4I aspects in every GEP. While innovative and impactful elements were relatively easier to address – particularly because innovation relates to specific national or local contexts – inclusiveness and intersectionality proved more challenging for participants who were new to structural projects and to working in a sector such as sport, which has traditionally operated in silos and remains far removed from an intersectional approach. For this reason, intersectionality and inclusiveness were emphasised in several of the mutual learning activities and the update of the institutional roadmaps.

3. Mutual Learning Programme

The mutual learning programme consists of a series of systematic mutual learning activities spanning over the duration of the capacity building scheme. The programme aimed to facilitate the consolidation of insights and experiences acquired throughout the training programme, assist and inspire the co-design and implementation phases of the institutional roadmaps, and enable the exchange of ideas, best practices and challenges among the consortium IOs.

The mutual learning programme comprised the following activities:

- Three offline 1.5-day mutual learning workshops which followed the completion of each training module.
- Five online half-day mutual learning sessions. Both face-to-face workshops and online sessions involved the active participation of all IOs and were designed and delivered by the SUPPORTER core team.
- Two bilateral mutual learning meetings among IOs.
- Seven learning diaries by each IO submitted periodically.

The following subsections provide a detailed overview of the content of the aforementioned activities and their main objectives. The agendas of all mutual learning workshops and sessions, as well as the templates of the learning diaries can be found in Annexes 2 and 3.

3.1 Mutual Learning Workshops

The three mutual learning workshops were strategically planned after the completion of each training module to provide IOs with the opportunity to consolidate and capitalise on the knowledge acquired during the trainings. Through each of the workshops, IOs were able to develop a sound understanding of issues pertaining to gender+ equality and the design of GEPs, engage in constructive dialogue, and share best practices, experiences and challenges to facilitate the development of their 4I-GEPs.

The workshops had the following objectives:

- Enable knowledge transfer and consolidation of the information acquired during the training modules.
- Prepare IOs for the institutional mapping, the co-design and implementation of the institutional roadmaps.
- Foster reflections and discussions among IOs on best practices and lived experiences.

Similar to the training modules, the workshops covered an array of gender+ equality topics ranging from baseline issues, such as the distinction between gender balance and gender equality, to complex themes including intersectionality and sustainability of GEPs. They were conducted face-to-face and lasted 1.5 days. All workshops started with an introduction, followed by reflexive exercises on the knowledge IOs had acquired through each training module, as well as various mutual learning activities that facilitated the exchange of ideas and practices.

3.1.1 Mutual Learning Workshop I

The first mutual learning workshop took place in Strasbourg, France in September 2023 and aimed at introducing the mutual learning programme to the IOs as well as providing them with the opportunity to consolidate the learnings of the first training module. More specifically, the workshop covered the following topics:

- Introduction to the mutual learning programme: mutual learning workshops and sessions, bilateral meetings, learning diaries and expectations
- Reflection on national and institutional gender equality frameworks and policies
- Reflection on Training Module I
- Introduction to reflexive self-assessment of T2.3

The tools employed for the first workshop include an ice-breaking activity, presentations by both IOs and the core team, roundtable discussions and a World Café exercise. IOs worked in cross-institutional groups to allow knowledge transfer and interactive dialogue, and were assisted by core team members who acted as facilitators. The results of each exercise were discussed in the plenary by group rapporteurs.

3.1.2 Mutual Learning Workshop II

The second mutual learning workshop took place in Thessaloniki, Greece in June 2024 and aimed at integrating an intersectional approach to the implementation of the institutional roadmaps and the development of Gender Equality Plans, exploring how the values and principles of sports can contribute to the promotion of gender equality in the academic environment and society in general, and collecting insights into the effective implementation of institutional roadmaps. The workshop addressed the following topics:

- The role of intersectionality in institutional change in the academic environment
- Reflection on Training module II on data collection, strategic framing and monitoring indicators
- Intersecting inequalities in the implementing organisations
- Embedding intersectionality in strategic framing and monitoring indicators
- Reflection on the first months of roadmap implementation
- The role of sports in the promotion of gender equality in the society

The workshop included presentations by IOs, core team members and invited experts, exercises followed by roundtable discussions, as well as activities in breakout rooms with the results being reported in the plenary by each group afterwards.

3.1.3 Mutual Learning Workshop III

The third mutual learning workshop was held in Ljubljana, Slovenia in March 2025 and intended to explore the 4I concepts focusing on innovation, impact, and inclusiveness, leverage roadmap insights to support the effective drafting of new institutional GEPs, and collect project learnings to draft policy recommendations for advancing gender equality in sports higher education. The workshop addressed the following topics:

- Reflection on Training Module III
- Putting the 4I-GEP theory into practice in the new GEPs
- Comparative analysis of good practices and new priorities in the 4I-GEPs
- Strategic steps for the successful implementation of sustainable GEPs
- Policy recommendations for advancing gender equality in sports higher education

The workshop included presentations by the core team and invited experts, and exercises in breakout rooms followed by plenary discussions. During the activities each implementing

organisation was paired with another institution in order to exchange ideas and experiences, and actively contribute to the mutual learning process.

3.2 Mutual Learning Sessions

Five online half-day mutual learning sessions were organised periodically throughout the project to cater for the needs of the eight sports universities/faculties during the roadmap implementation process, and address any challenges or obstacles. Moreover, the sessions provided IOs with the opportunity to discuss their developing 4I-GEPs with their peers and share good practices.

The mutual learning sessions had the following objectives:

1. Inform IOs about the co-creation and implementation process and the key steps to be taken.
2. Offer guidance and support to IOs during the roadmap implementation phase by addressing challenges and obstacles.
3. Provide IOs with the opportunity to exchange ideas and reflect on good practices that will inform their 4I-GEPs and facilitate the roadmap implementation.
4. Contribute to the development of sustainable 4I-GEPs with a clear focus on sports education.

The mutual learning sessions focused on the following themes:

- Mutual learning session I: Introduction to Roadmaps: Co-design.
- Mutual learning session II: Roadmap Implementation: Challenges and Engagement of Stakeholders.
- Mutual learning session III: Roadmap Implementation: Focus on Sports Education Institutions.
- Mutual learning session IV: Roadmap Implementation: Gender-based Violence.
- Mutual learning session V: Reflections on the SUPPORTER Journey.

3.2.1 Mutual Learning Session I

The first session took place in December 2023 and was designed to offer a comprehensive introduction to the roadmap co-design process and deepen IOs' understanding of central concepts related to roadmap design. Moreover, it aimed at engaging IOs in internal stakeholder mapping, which was an integral part of the co-design process, and finally elucidating potentially confusing terms such as gender equality vs. gender balance, 4Is, change agents etc. The session addressed the following topics:

- Reflection on the self-assessment exercise
- Clarification of key concepts
- Internal stakeholder mapping
- Introduction to University of Gothenburg gender equality policy as good practice
- Introduction to roadmaps and co-design

The session explored the aforementioned topics through presentations delivered by the core team and the implementing organisations, as well as a series of group work activities in which members from different IOs collaborated effectively and shared valuable insights.

3.2.2 Mutual Learning Session II

The second session, which was held in March 2024, focused on the challenges IOs were expected to face during roadmap implementation, particularly in relation to stakeholder engagement. More specifically, the session aimed at providing IOs with the opportunity to discuss and reflect on the expected challenges in the implementation of Grounding Actions, exploring tools and methods to facilitate internal stakeholder engagement, and introduce the learning diaries. The session covered the following topics:

- Reflection on roadmap co-creation and implementation: engagement with internal and external stakeholders
- Tools and methods to engage with stakeholders
- Introduction to learning diaries

The session included several group activities which were held in breakout rooms, as well as presentations to the plenary. Each IO reflected on the roadmap co-creation process and received constructive and valuable feedback from members of other institutions. Moreover, the introduction of new tools and methods to foster stakeholder engagement as well as the presentation of the learning diaries was followed by exercises to reinforce IOs' knowledge of the newly introduced concepts and enhance mutual learning.

3.2.3 Mutual Learning Session III

The third session took place in September 2024 and explored Gender Equality in Sports Education Institutions. The session aimed at discussing lessons learned from the recently held Olympics and Paralympics 2024 regarding gender equality in sports, exchanging good gender equality practices in sports higher education institutions and academic departments, and ensuring the integration of an intersectional approach in the implementation of institutional roadmaps and ensuing Gender Equality Plans.

The session discussed the following topics:

- IOC's 2024 objectives and guidelines for gender equality in sports: good practices and steps forward
- Intersectionality: lessons learned in mutual learning workshop II
- Inspiring sports-related practices that promote gender equality in the sports environment

The session included presentations by implementing organisations and the core team, as well as group exercises. As all IOs are sports higher education universities/faculties, the focus on the Olympics and Paralympics 2024 generated fruitful discussions and meaningful reflections on gender equality in sports education.

3.2.4 Mutual Learning Session IV

The fourth mutual learning session, which was held in December 2024, focused on broadening IOs' understanding of gender-based violence, especially regarding its different types and its connection to sports, higher education institutions, 4I-GEPs and sustainability. It also involved discussions and reflections on the challenges IOs encountered in the implementation of Grounding Actions and the necessary revisions they need to make to address gender-based violence. Finally, emphasis was placed on the sustainability of the roadmap actions beyond the project's lifecycle,

and on supporting knowledge exchange and network expansion through participation in Communities of Practice.

The session addressed the following topics:

- Roadmap development: steps forward
- Gender-based violence
- Sustainability of GEPs
- Communities of Practice

The session featured presentations and activities designed to introduce key terms and enhance IOs' understanding, allowing them to express their own viewpoints and experiences, and learn from the experience of others.

3.2.5 Mutual Learning Session V

The fifth session, which took place in June 2025, explored IOs' reflections on their participation in the project and the co-design and implementation of their roadmaps. More specifically, the session aimed to foster self-awareness by encouraging core team and IO members to share their personal and institutional reflections on the planning, implementation, and impact of SUPPORTER, identify key learnings and transformative experiences gained through the project at individual level. It also helped them explore how the project contributed to organisational change through promoting and embedding gender equality, and initiate a conversation on post-SUPPORTER research interests and funding opportunities to build on the project's momentum.

The session covered the following topics:

- Reflections on the SUPPORTER project
- Reflecting on reflections
- Research after SUPPORTER: interests and funding opportunities.

Contrary to previous sessions that included many group activities in breakout rooms, this last session only featured plenary presentations and discussions to ensure that all ideas were heard by different organisations and that each experience was cherished and celebrated. The session provided IOs and the core team with the opportunity to contemplate on the successes and challenges of the project and discuss future actions.

3.3 Bilateral Meetings

Two bilateral mutual learning meetings were held among pairs of IOs during the roadmap implementation period. IOs were paired based on the similarities of their roadmaps and institutional context to ensure fruitful discussions and common points of interest.

The bilateral meetings had the following objectives:

- Provide IOs with the opportunity to exchange experiences, strategies, and feedback on the implementation of their institutional roadmaps.
- Provide a safe environment where IOs can discuss potential challenges in the definition of the 4I-GEPs.

Face-to-face meetings were deemed more effective as IOs tended to feel more comfortable to express their ideas, share concerns and discuss the progress of their roadmaps in physical rather than online encounters. To this purpose, the two bilateral meetings were scheduled during the second and third mutual learning workshops, in Thessaloniki and Ljubljana respectively. The first round of bilateral meetings focused on the success of Grounding Actions and challenges in the implementation of the roadmap until that point, while the second involved the reflections of IOs on the first year of institutional roadmap implementation. IOs appreciated the opportunity to have one-to-one discussions with partners from a different, yet similar, organisation and often opted for a different lingua franca – other than English – which facilitated the interactions and yielded meaningful conclusions. Moreover, IOs were encouraged to continue the bilateral discussions online and capitalise on this unique opportunity to exchange ideas and learn from one another.

3.4 Learning Diaries

The adoption of learning diaries was instrumental for the effectiveness of the mutual learning programme as they complemented all other activities by engaging IOs in a process of self-analysis and reflexivity. Through the completion of seven learning diaries, which function as field books, implementing organisations not only recorded the actions and activities completed during the project period, but also reflected on the training, co-design and implementation process. Out of the seven learning diaries, diaries 2, 3, 4, 6 and 7 focused on the implementation of roadmaps, while diaries 1 and 5 addressed issues pertaining to the three training modules to ensure that the trainings offered under the capacity building scheme were both relevant and essential to IOs. Moreover, learning diaries formed the basis for the discussions held during the M&Ms IOs had with their mentors, and were among the data analysed for the development of guidelines and recommendations on gender mainstreaming and addressing gender-based violence in sports education under T4.3. IOs received detailed guidance on the completion of each diary and were provided with the respective templates (see Annex 3).

More specifically, learning diary 1 addressed the learnings of training modules I and II and discussed the operationalisation of gender, gender equality, intersectionality, gender-based violence, and gender equality in sports in each IO's context, as well as internal stakeholder engagement and further training needs. Learning diaries 2, 3, and 4 requested IOs' insights on the activities completed during the respective reporting periods and to identify the best practices, challenges and future steps. Learning diary 5 built upon the knowledge acquired during training module III and focused on IOs' recommendations to similar organisations regarding gender equality, structural change, and intersectionality. Learning diary 6 addressed the roadmap implementation process holistically by focusing on all Grounding Actions, thus providing IOs with

the opportunity to reflect on the completion of the actions based on the criteria they had set in their roadmaps. Finally, the last learning diary asked IOs to reflect on the integration of the 4Is in their new GEPs.

3.5 Timeline

The tables below provides information about the timeline, content, format and participants of all activities of the mutual learning programme.

	Topic	Format	Numbers of Participants	Month/Date
Mutual Learning Workshop I	Introduction to the mutual learning programme Reflection on the first training module Introduction to the self-reflexive exercise	Offline (Strasbourg)	33	M6, September 2023
Mutual Learning Session I	Introduction to Roadmaps: Co-design	Online	26	M9, December 2023
Mutual Learning Session II	Roadmap implementation: Challenges and engagement of stakeholders	Online	33	M12, March 2024
Mutual Learning Workshop II	Reflection on Training Module II: Gender+ segregated data and state/local policies and regulations	Offline (Thessaloniki)	29	M15, June 2024
Mutual Learning Session III	Roadmap implementation: Focus on sports education institutions	Online	33	M18, September 2024
Mutual Learning Session IV	Roadmap Implementation: Gender-based violence	Online	43	M21, December 2024
Mutual Learning Workshop III	Reflection on Training Module III: GEP implementation, monitoring and evaluation	Offline (Ljubljana)	31	M24, March 2025
Mutual Learning Session V	Reflections on the SUPPORTER Journey	Online	19	M27, June 2025

	Topic	Format	Participants	Date/Month
Bilateral Meeting I	Roadmap implementation	Offline (Thessaloniki)	Among IOs	M15, June 2024
Bilateral Meeting II	Roadmap implementation	Offline (Ljubljana)	Among IOs	M24, March 2025
Learning Diary I	Training Module I&II	N/A	Completed by IOs, discussed in MMMs	M12, March 2024
Learning Diary II	Roadmap implementation	N/A	Completed by IOs, discussed in MMMs	M14, May 2024
Learning Diary III	Roadmap implementation	N/A	Completed by IOs, discussed in MMMs	M18, September 2024
Learning Diary IV	Roadmap implementation	N/A	Completed by IOs, discussed in MMMs	M21, December 2024
Learning Diary V	Training Module III (4I-GEP)	N/A	Completed by IOs, discussed in MMMs	M22, January 2025
Learning Diary VI	Roadmap implementation	N/A	Completed by IOs, discussed in MMMs	M25, April 2025
Learning Diary VII	Roadmap implementation	N/A	Completed by IOs, discussed in MMMs	M28, July 2025

3.6 Feedback from Participants

After every mutual learning event, participants received a link to a short survey requesting both quantitative and qualitative feedback. More specifically, attendees were asked to rate certain aspects of the workshops/sessions, such as tempo, structure, content etc. on a scale of 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest), as well as provide open-ended feedback.

Overall, participant feedback was highly positive with an average of 4.65 (ranging from 4.25 to 4.85) for all events. With regard to individual comments, a few attendees requested more time to complete group exercises after participating in the first two workshops/sessions. These comments were seriously considered and led to an increase in the duration of the exercises. Participants found the presentations of the third mutual learning session very well balanced and well-delivered and the fourth session very well organised. They also particularly enjoyed the third mutual learning workshop which they considered extremely effective and fruitful. In particular, one participant expressed their satisfaction about exchanging experiences and meeting competent people with the same vision and approaches. This showcases the crucial role the mutual learning programme has

played in fostering a sense of belonging and community among partners. Similarly, two attendees of the last session stressed the importance and usefulness of the teamwork and networking opportunities they had during the event.

3.7 Self-assessment by Organisers

The mutual learning programme has largely succeeded in achieving its objectives, namely to consolidate the insights and experiences IOs acquired during the trainings, assist and inspire the co-creation and implementation of institutional roadmaps and 4I-GEPs, and enable the exchange of best practices, ideas, challenges and concerns among IOs.

More specifically, throughout the mutual learning workshops and sessions IOs had the opportunity to revise their learnings from the training programme and enhance their understanding of fundamental concepts that were essential for the development of the Grounding Actions. They were also able to discuss various issues pertaining to gender equality in sports with their peers, the core team and invited experts, and as a result become increasingly aware of diverse perspectives and experiences.

Similarly to the training modules, an important factor that affected the design and content of the mutual learning events was the varying level of knowledge among IOs. To ensure a common understanding, it was necessary to reintroduce many gender-related terms and concepts. This was especially important as participants came from different ethnic, cultural and professional backgrounds and had different knowledge, experiences and concerns. The different levels of knowledge also affected group work. Depending on the topic and the learning outcomes of each session, more advanced participants were paired with less experienced IOs or same-level participants were paired together. The collaboration with different partners benefitted tremendously IOs, as they broadened their understanding of gender equality, identified common problems and solutions, and shared good practices.

Another challenge was to help IOs understand the relevance and applicability of the issues discussed to their institutions and 4I-GEPs. At the beginning of the project, some IOs had a limited grasp of gender equality, often considering it a synonym for gender balance. Thus, for them achieving gender balance among staff in their institution was viewed as the only action towards gender equality. Different types of resistance were also prevalent among IOs initially preventing them from accepting and integrating new information (Vilarchao et al., 2025). Moreover, some IO members had difficulty perceiving concepts such as intersectionality and gender+. To overcome these challenges, confusing terms were explained multiple times in different contexts using meaningful and specific examples to ensure they would be understood and effectively integrated into Grounding Actions and roadmaps.

Regarding the organisation of the workshops and sessions, initially group activities were allotted insufficient time, something which was reflected in participants' feedback. Following the first few sessions, more time was allocated to group work and core team presentations were limited to 20 minutes. Furthermore, the mode of delivery affected participation levels. IO members were significantly more active, vocal and productive during offline workshops, than in online sessions. To overcome this challenge, the content of some online sessions was extended over two days instead of one, as there was a considerable decrease in participation levels after the first two hours. For the same reason, the three face-to-face workshops were ideal for the introduction of important tasks and templates, such as roadmap co-design and the completion of the learning diaries.

With regard to the learning diaries, their role was pivotal for the successful design, revision and implementation of the roadmaps as they helped clarify misconceptions, evaluate work-in-progress, assess short-term outcomes, and envision the post-project implementation period of the 4I-GEPs. They also functioned as the basis for the discussions held during the M&Ms between the core team and IOs.

Overall, despite the challenges, the mutual learning programme achieved its purpose and contributed significantly to the overarching aim of the project, which was the development and implementation of eight inclusive, innovative, intersectional and impactful gender equality plans.

4. Mentoring and Monitoring Scheme

The Mentoring and Monitoring Scheme oversaw and guided the co-design and implementation of the institutional roadmaps with the help of the project's core team, and facilitated the development of post-project long-term 4I-GEPs. More specifically, the scheme enabled IOs to self-evaluate the design and development of Grounding Actions, which constitute the backbone of roadmaps. It also enabled the core team to monitor and advise IOs on the creation and execution of their roadmaps with a long-term vision, preparing them for the period beyond the end of the project. The scheme comprised eight M&Ms held on a regular basis between core team members and each IO, although many more ad hoc meetings were scheduled on a needs basis with most of the partners.

Through self-reflection and by creating a safe and welcoming environment, the SUPPORTER core team helped IOs assess the progress and effectiveness of their Grounding Actions, report good practices, consolidate learnings, share experiences as well as identify training needs. As a result, IOs' participation in the M&Ms contributed significantly to the achievement of the roadmap objectives and, ultimately, to the development of comprehensive, realistic and sustainable 4I-GEPs, capable of gender-related institutional change, whose actions and outcomes will exceed the SUPPORTER project's lifespan.

Regarding the content of each meeting, the first meeting, which took place offline in Strasbourg in September 2023, introduced IOs to the scheme and the roadmap co-creation, while the second addressed IOs' responses to the self-assessment exercises and clarified misconceptions. During the third and fourth meeting, the SUPPORTER core team assisted IOs in the challenging and complex task of the roadmap co-design that constituted the cornerstone of the ensuing 4I-GEPs. Out of the remaining meetings, some capitalised on the reflections and insights the IOs shared in their learning diaries and gave IOs both the time and space to adjust and refine their Grounding Actions and overcome potential challenges and obstacles, while others were dedicated to the development and refinement of the 4I-GEPs.

4.1 Timeline

	Topic of discussion	Format	Date
M&M 1	Induction to the mentoring and monitoring scheme	Offline	M6, September 2023
M&M 2	Self-assessment exercise (T2.3)	Online	M8, Nov 2023
M&M 3	Co-design of roadmap	Online	M10, January 2024
M&M 4	Co-design of roadmap (part II)	Online	M11, February 2024

M&M 5	Learning Diary 2 (Implementation of roadmap)	Offline	M15, June 2024
M&M 6	Learning Diary 3 (Implementation of roadmap)	Online	M19, Oct 2024
M&M 7	Learning Diary 4 (Implementation of roadmap)	Online	M22, Jan 2025
M&M 8	Learning Diary 6 and 7 (Implementation of roadmap - Update of GEP into 4I-GEP)	Online	M26, May 2025

Conclusions

The horizontal capacity building scheme has undoubtedly been instrumental in the successful co-design and implementation of the eight institutional roadmaps and subsequent 4I-GEPs. Its comprehensive, interconnected and complementary components: the training programme, the mutual learning programme, and the mentoring and monitoring scheme provided implementing organisations with the essential knowledge and practical skills necessary for the development of new GEPs focusing on gender-based violence and gender+ equality in sports higher education.

More specifically, the training programme through its three modules and nine training sessions succeeded in equipping IOs with gender-specific knowledge and strategies to foster gender equality and act as change agents in their own institutions. To this end, it was significantly assisted by the mutual learning programme that facilitated the consolidation of knowledge and the exchange of ideas and good practices among IOs, effectively creating a safe space for IOs to collaborate and express their viewpoints. Moreover, through the completion of the learning diaries, IOs had the opportunity to reflect on the co-creation and implementation process of their roadmaps, revisit their objectives and priorities, and evaluate the progress of their own work. Finally, the mentoring and monitoring scheme facilitated the collaboration between the core team and IOs, providing both parties adequate space and time to discuss the roadmap co-design and implementation, address concerns, problems and challenges, and propose solutions. It also contributed to establishing a sense of trust, belonging, and community.

Despite its success, the scheme encountered important challenges. The online delivery of training and mutual learning sessions was less effective than face-to-face workshops due to decreased participation and productivity. Additionally, the varying levels of knowledge and the diverse cultural backgrounds of the implementing organisations affected the design of the training and mutual learning sessions, as well as the allocation of members during group work. Finally, and more importantly, misconceptions about gender equality, unconscious biases, and resistance from certain partners influenced the pace and content of some sessions.

Nevertheless, the adaptability and flexibility of the horizontal capacity building scheme allowed the adjustment of content and rearrangement of priorities to ensure an efficient and meaningful learning experience for all IOs, regardless of their background, prior knowledge, and cultural differences. In fact, the scheme utilised such discrepancies to its benefit by tailoring the training and mutual learning content and materials, and the mentoring and monitoring meetings to the needs of individual organisations.

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Annex 1 – Training Programme Scripts

Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with Intersectional, Innovative and Inclusive Gender Equality Plans

SUPPORTER Training Programme

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Introduction

This document outlines the design of the SUPPORTER training programme. It is based on the mappings carried out in WP2. The training programme consists of three modules, each delivering three ½ day sessions on:

- Module I: Basic training on key concepts, institutional change, gender equality and Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) (M9, September)
- Module II: Intermediate training on gender equality and Inclusive and progressive GEPs
- Module III: Advanced training on gender equality in sports higher education and research institutions, including 4I-GEPs (M

Modules II and III are developed based on the outcomes of WP2 (T2.2 & T2.3), feedback from Module I, and from the Mutual Learning Workshops and mentoring activities.

Training Modules

MODULE I: Basic training on key concepts, institutional change, gender equality, gender-based violence and GEPs

This first of three modules is a basic training to ensure a shared understanding of key concepts and contexts. It addresses:

- Main issues at stake regarding gender equality in research and higher education in the context of sport
 - Prevalence and consequences of gender-based violence in the European Research Area
- Key concepts, e.g., gender, gender+, intersectionality, gender-based violence;
- Policies on gender equality and gender-based violence in the European Research Area
- GEP as the main instrument towards institutional change. Introduction to the 6 steps of a GEP.
- Learn about prerequisites and key success factors of institutional change processes.
- Gain awareness about how to facilitate change and how to deal with resistances.

The module consists of three ½ day sessions (9:30-13:00). The three scripts (1a, 1b and 1c below), respectively each cover one of those ½ day sessions

Learning objectives

Session 1: key concepts and shared understanding

- Creating awareness of what is at stake, why gender equality and addressing gender-based violence are important
 - Building knowledge on gender-based violence (prevalence and consequences) in the ERA
- Creating a shared understanding of key concepts, including gender, gender+, intersectionality and gender-based violence.
- Gender-based violence: prevalence and consequences in the European Research Area

Session 2: institutional change

- Creating a baseline and shared understanding of institutional change in higher education institutions
- Identifying routes to institutional change towards gender+ equality
- Identifying the key components of an institutional gender+ (equality analysis)

Session 3: Gender equality plans

- Designing a gender equality plan (GEP):
- Key components of a GEP
- Dealing with resistances and challenges to gender+ equality and GEP implementation

- Supporting gender equality change agents

Ideal target group

- Gender equality officers/Diversity officers and Senior managers
- GEP teams/team members (people involved in gender equality plans on a regular basis)
- Human resources officers
- Middle managers
- Other stakeholders directly involved in driving institutional change processes

Materials

- D2.1
- Appendix 1
- Appendix 2
- UniSAFE Glossary on gender-based violence in higher education and research organisations
- GEAR-tool steps of GEPs
- Miro or google drive for work in subgroups. Posters for face-to-face training.
- Exit questionnaire

Content outline

Session 1, 1 September 09:30-13:00, online

- What's at stake?
 - Problems related to gender, gender+ and intersectionality
 - Defining gender equality, gender equality strategies and approaches
 - Gender-based violence in the higher education context: prevalence and consequences
- Key concepts: gender, gender+, intersectionality
- Key concepts: gender-based violence, including sexual harassment
- Exercise/group work

Session 2: 7 September 09:30 – 13:00, online,

- European Commission framing
- Institutional change: definitions and pathways
- Institutional change, gender equality, and gender-based violence in HEI
- Introduction to gender equality plans
- Institutional gender+ (equality) analysis

Session 3 (14 September, Strasbourg)

- Implementing gender+ equality
- Key components of a gender equality plan (GEP) -
- Dealing with resistances and challenges to gender+ equality and GEP implementation
- Supporting gender equality change agents – Stakeholder mapping.

Script 1a: Shared understanding of key concepts – 1 September, online

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations	Suggested trainer
9:30	Introduction	Welcome Introduction to SUPPORTER Presentation of programme Presentation of the three modules & today	2 min 4 min 4 min	Welcome Recording-consent Ask ppl to add their names to zoom window PPT: Introduction to SUPPORTER PPT	ESF Ildi ESF Eugenia UGOT Sofia
9:40	Expectations	What are your expectations of today's training? What do you hope to learn from this module?	5 min	Mentimeter – to prepare and share link in chat. https://www.menti.com/alcaqmevezft Responses to be used at the end of the session to compare with final reflections Housekeeping rules	UGOT Sofia
9:45	Presentations and getting to know each other	Introductions two and two in break-out rooms. One person introduces the other in plenary	45 min	Aim is to establish collegiality and to get to know each other, as we will be working together in nine training sessions.	UGOT Sofia
10:30	Break		10 min		
10:40	Gender equality in research and academia: what is at stake	Introduction to some of the main issues related to gender equality in higher education/research:	20 min	PPT	SEERC Zoi

		vertical and horizontal segregation, precariousness, international mobility, and gender bias. Understanding why the promotion of gender equality is important.			
11:00	GBV in HEI: what's at stake – prevalence and consequences	Introduce definition, prevalence and consequences incl. across different groups in HEI	5 min	PPT	UGOT Sofia
11:05	Key concepts on gender, gender+, intersectionality, gender equality	Introduction of key concepts, with the aim to bring everybody to the same page re concepts and debates. Understanding gender equality and gender equality approaches.	20 min	PPT Short session to ensure the same baseline understanding. Use D2.1 for key concepts; consider developing a glossary – potentially use the one we are developing in UniSAFE. Participants' knowledge will vary greatly, some are likely to be experts whereas others are beginners – important to get everyone on board with the same vocabulary to understand/describe gender, gender+, intersectionality and gender equality.	UGOT Karin
11:25	Questions/concerns	Ask participants for any questions, needs for clarifications	5 min		UGOT Sofia, all
11:30	Group work	Introducing a set of statements to discuss/agree on their resonance with gender equality & GBV in HEI Group work	5 min 25 min	Introduction The statements/ sentences are shown on a PP and in the shared document on SharePoint, where participants can also make some notes). In break out rooms, the participants discuss them and the ways in which they are about gender equality and/or GBV, and how? Break out rooms, four break out room; ensure mix of core partners and IOs per room	UGOT Suzanne
12:00	Break		10 min		
12:10	Discussion: report from break-out rooms; reflections and takeaways	Reporting back from group work; three main takeaways.	30 min	Each group reports back in plenary and are asked to list their three main takeaways; facilitator connects back to the initial centimetre results on expectations	UGOT Suzanne
12:40	Summary	Summary of key observations Exit questionnaire	10 min		UGOT Sofia/Suz
12:50	Conclusions	Next steps, dates etc.	5 min		Sofia
13:00	End				

Script 1b: Shared understanding of institutional change (7 September)

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations	trainer
9:30	Introduction	Introduction to SUPPORTER Recap of session 1	5 min 10 min	Welcome Recording Brief recap of the outcomes of the first session. Questionnaire results	ESF Eugenia
9:45	Warming up	Ask participants to share expectations for today, or what they would like to learn more about	5 min	Participants to write in chat, for us to copy. https://www.menti.com/aldij9ye57y8 Responses can be used at the end of the session	ESF Zoom chat and mentimeter
09:50	Aims and programme	Present session aims and programme slide	5 min	Show the programme of today Ground rules Today's training programme	UGOT Sofia
09:45	Institutional change: definitions and pathways	European Commission approach to transforming higher education and research institutions and to the current status quo in implementing institutional change in the EU/Europe From fixing women to fixing organisations: pathways to institutional change	15 min	Aim is to identify routes to institutional change towards gender+ equality Presenting the three main objectives of the EU?	ESF Eugenia
10:00	Institutional change: general + definitions, pathways	Institutional change from a broader perspective	10 min	Introduce (based on previous structural change projects) and create link with later presentations in this session	ESF Eugenia
10:20	Institutional change & gender	Definition and main objectives of institutional change, in a gender equality context	10 min	Aim is to create a baseline and shared understanding of institutional change	UGOT Nathalie
10:30	Intro to GEP as a tool to	What is a GEP, why are they	20	Aim is to introduce GEPs as a tool to institutional change (to set the base for the	UGOT Nathalie

	institutional change	central; name the components		third session); note that all IOs have a GEP, as it was a requirement for funding	
10:50	Group discussion	Does your institution's GEP cover the elements just presented?	10 min	Short small discussion, two people in each breakout room.	UGOT Nathalie introduces
11:00	Reporting back	20 min		Round of reflections / feedback on discussion in break-out rooms	
11:20	Break	10 min			Take photo after the break
11:30	Gender equality analysis	Gender equality analysis What should be included? (first step of a GEP)	20	Outline of how to conduct a gender equality analysis, its steps and components. 1. Identify what data your institution is already collecting and put them together 2. Identify all types of data you need to additionally collect 3. Identify possible sources of information and techniques to collect data 4. Review relevant legislation and policies 5. Collect and analyse data	UGOT Nathalie
11:50	Group discussion	Gender equality analysis in the IOs Recap; prepare for reporting back in plenary	30 min	Participants in groups of 5 discuss their experiences of gender equality analysis in their organisations Take 5 minutes to recap on what was said and what to present in plenary: what is the crucial data needed, is it collected already, or is there a gap	All Core partners participate in the rooms, only if needed we act as rapporteurs
12:20	Reporting back, shared reflections	Lessons from gender equality analysis	20 min	Participants report the main results from discussion in their institutions from doing a GE analysis Reactions from other groups	UGOT Suzanne facilitates; Nathalie functions as a discussant
12:40	Success factors		5 min		Nathalie, names the success factors to end this part of the session
12:45	Summary reflections	Feedback questionnaire	5 min	https://forms.office.com/e/DYwm72bJDj	ESF Eugenia
12:50	Conclusions	Next steps, dates etc.	5 min		ESF Eugenia
12:525	End				

Script 1c: Shared understanding of GEPs – 14 September, offline

- Implementing gender+ equality
- Key components of a gender equality plan (GEP): focus on stakeholder mapping
 - Supporting gender equality change agents in identifying stakeholders

- Introducing resistances and challenges to gender+ equality and GEP implementation

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
9:30	Introduction	Welcome and practicalities	10 min	ESF
9:40	Warming up	Recap the evaluation, ask about key aspect they found interesting from last two sessions	10 min	Summarise the evaluation, and how we take it into account. - E.g. more time for discussion in the ML Ask about a take-away from last session ESF
09:50	Key components of a GEP	Brief recap on institutional change and GEP as an instrument 6 steps of a GEP	10 min	ESF-Eugenia
10:00	Stakeholder mapping	Introduction of content, steps etc. Change agents, core team, network of allies	10 min	UGOT Nathalie
10:10	Group work on stakeholder mapping	Small groups; 5-6 at each table	20 min group work 10 min recap (Nat)	UGOT - Nathalie does a round by each table. Need a facilitator at each table. Stakeholder mapping in subgroups. For the mapping, it is important to get concrete stakeholders identified so for example NOT leaders BUT: head of the Faculty of Sport. NOT networks BUT networks of female scientists or network of female coaches.
10:40	Key success factors	Presentation of key success factors, incl.: Get support; Resources; Involvement of key stakeholders; Embedded in existing structures; Data available gender+; Set clear targets and practical, objectives; Capacity building; Monitor and evaluate; Flexibility and resilient	5-7 min	UGOT –Nathalie recaps briefly
10:45	Identifying the challenges in your institutions	Individual exercise Ask the participants to choose which of the success factors that provide the biggest challenges in their institution.	7-10	UGOT - Suzanne React individually what the key challenges are, concretely. Each participant is given three blue stickers to place on a poster under the challenge they choose. Can put all three stickers under one, or split as they prefer.

				Use flip chart or large paper with the key success factors listed, ESF has printed the poster for participants to put their stickers on
10:55	Break	If needed, participants can use some break time to allocate sticker	20	UGOT to prepare lotus blossom during the break (core challenge), and recap of facilitation methods Materials needed: post-it notes, pens/markers. UGOT: prepare stakeholder poster and lotus blossom to ask ESF to print in A3
11:15	Group work: identifying the problem(s)	Presenting the results of the blue stickers: main risks and obstacles, Presenter chooses the three challenges with the bluest stickers	5 min	Introducing group work – four groups UGOT- Nathalie
11:20		Work on Lotus blossom in four groups	30 min	Use the Lotus blossom prepared during the break. Session of brainstorming, no need to agree/disagree. 1 st level: core problem in the middle (e.g. lack of resources), facilitator: what potential solutions to the problem? If the same idea for a solution is raised, put the same sticker/post it in the box, then measures . Facilitators: Eugenia, Zoi, Karin, Suzanne
11:50	Sharing presenting	Everybody	20 min	Walk around the posters, one person from each group presents their challenge and 'solution' Each group shares the results: facilitators present if no-one else has volunteered.
12:10	Resistance framework	Introduce the resistance framework	10 min	Nathalie presents the typology
12:30	Experiences of resistance	Increase understanding of resistance framework	20 min	Examples of institutional resistance in our own lives (ESF)
12:50	Takeaways	Main takeaways	10 min	ESF if time: pick up on gender equality; substantial vs numerical.
13:00	End			

MODULE II: Intermediate training on gender equality and inclusive and intersectional gender equality plans

This second of three modules is an intermediate training to increase knowledge and facilitate the design of IOs' gender equality plans in the sports environment. It builds on the first module of shared understanding, the mutual learning workshops and work carried out by the IOs T2.1 and T2.3. The focus of the training is the second and third steps of the gender equality plan: analysing

and assessing the state-of-play in the institution, and setting up a gender equality plan, with a focus on sports education.

The plan was to have three ½ day online sessions (two hours before lunch and two hours after lunch) on 4 April, 25 April, and 30 May 2024. The timing was adapted after session 1, starting earlier) following the request of participants to have it fitting in one half-day.

Content

- Session 1: Analysis and assessment of the state-of-play in the institution; data collection, and data analysis; focus on sport higher education institutions
- Session 2: Analysis and assessment of the state-of-play in the institution: measures and policy; focus on sport higher education institutions
- Session 3: Setting up a gender equality plan; indicators and monitoring; focus on sport higher education institutions

Learning objectives

- Creating knowledge on the analysis and assessment of the state-of-play in the institution
- Setting up a gender equality plan
- Supporting self-reflection on one's own priority sets and change strategies
- Mutual learning and exchange: Getting inspiration from others

Ideal target group

- Change agents
 - GEP teams/team members (people involved in gender equality plans design and implementation)
 - Data analysts; staff in charge of data collection, data analysis

Preparations by the IOs

- Stakeholder mapping of the IOs (example exercise included in M1)
- Identification of core GEP team (example exercise included in M1)
- Inventory of available and relevant data, data on gender, ethnicity, age, disability in relation to equality

Materials

- D2.1, D3.1

- IOs Roadmaps
- Appendix 1 and Appendix 2

Miro link: https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVN2CcZ2Q=?share_link_id=208009883304

Script 2a: Intermediate training on gender equality and inclusive and intersectional GEPs: focus data – 4 April 2024

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
10:00	Welcome and introduction	Introduction to SUPPORTER training, including how this training connects to roadmaps & (the need for) grounded actions on data + relation to ML	10 min	Recording and photo consent ESF
10:10	Adding my role in the organisation Adding grounded actions GBV & data	Each IOs to put their grounded actions relating to data on sticky notes on Miro	20 min	Prepared Miro Use Miro to post name on sticky notes Aim: getting used to the Miro board + visualising grounded actions on data ESF
10:30	GE & GBV in sport	The sport higher education environment: key issues in relation to GE, GBV and I-sec	20 min	Anne-Laure Humbert, GenderSAFE project
10:50		Examples of GBV in sport; IOS to come up with and discuss concrete examples of gbv: could be forms of misconduct, bias, “misogyny” in sports (“a coach sharing misogynist comments to a woman student”) Continuum of gbv Sexism-rape Intersectionality	20 min	Anne-Laure introduces work in subgroups; four in each, discuss examples. Andreea: Participants in subgroup can be assigned randomly No Miro
11:10	Break		20 min	
11:30	Data collection on gender-based violence in higher education	<i>How do you collect data on these forms of violence?</i> Collecting gender+ intersectional data on gender equality and gender-based violence – Includes Q&A	30 min	Anne Laure Humbert Include Q&A
12:00	Lunch		60 min	
13:00	Data analysis on gender-based violence in higher education	Analysing gender+ intersectional data on gender equality and gender-based violence – Includes Q&A	30 min	Anne-Laure Humbert Include Q&A
13:30	Exercise on collecting data	<i>Identify the data you need to collect. What are your next steps?</i>	30 min	5 min intro (Nathalie) 25 min exercise Miro board

		<p>1. How does this apply to my institution? What is relevant for my orgs?</p> <p>2. What type of data can you collect? Who could do that or help?</p> <p>3. What do you prioritise?</p>		<p>Subgroup by IOs x 2 Facilitator per subgroup of two IOs; mentor to go to their subgroups</p> <p>5 min individual IOs on board 5 min sharing for each of the three questions</p> <p>Expect the 3rd question on the board to be difficult to address</p> <p>All partners</p>
14:00	Recap and next exercise	Plenary	10 min	<p>5 min looking back (“this was interesting, thanks for sharing”) (ALH)</p> <p>5 min intro to next exercise (NW)</p>
14:10	Exercise on analysing data	<p>What are your next steps?</p> <p>1. How does this apply to my institution? What is relevant for my orgs?</p> <p>2. Do you have the needed expertise? Where can you find it? Who to involve?</p> <p>3. What would you prioritise?</p>	30 min	<p>Miro board Subgroup by IOs x 2 Facilitator per subgroup of two IOs; mentor to go to their subgroups</p> <p>5 min individual IOs on board</p> <p>5 min sharing for each of the three questions</p> <p>Expect the 3rd question on the board to be difficult to address</p> <p>All partners</p>
14:40	Recap			Summary reflections ALH
14:50	Wrap up Recap	Instructions for what to do next, considering the results of the exercise Exit questionnaire, next steps, tasks for IOS	10 min	ESF Include how the training relates to coming tasks/activities
15:00	End			

Script 2b: Intermediate training on gender equality and inclusive and progressive GEPs – focus measures and policy – 25 April 2024

9-12 – shortened to enable the core group to attend

- Addressing the measures defined in the grounding actions
 - o Homework for IOs: which two grounded actions are you implementing first?
 - o Homework for us: send reading/preparatory instructions three weeks in advance.

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
9:00	Welcome and introduction	Introduction to the training , including how this training connects to roadmaps & (the need for) grounding actions on data + relation to ML	5 min	Recording and photo consent Please refer to the fact that this training is delivered by AGRIGEP ESF - Eugenia
9:05	Lecture	A step-by-step and strategic approach to GEP implementation. This sequence will highlight the need for clarifying objectives, setting up a self-monitoring framework and engaging with stakeholders. Most common challenges will be covered as well as potential solutions to overcome them.	20 min	Maxime Forest, Agrigep project. GEAR Step-by-step GEP approach RESET Checklist for GEP Monitoring
9:25	Q&A		5 min	
9:30	Lecture	A focus on addressing Gender-Based Violence through raising awareness and implementing comprehensive policies. This part of the lecture will bring recommendations about key steps for implementation and a set of resources and potential actions to tackle gender-based violence in HEI, with a particular attention to Sport education institutions.	25 min	Maxime, Nathalie UniSAFE step-by-step guide : Awareness-raising campaign on GBV UniSAFE step-by-step guide: Setting up a comprehensive policy framework addressing GBV in academia UniSAFE Guidelines : Developing a Protocol for addressing GBV in research and higher education institutions
	Q&A		5 min	
10:00	Break	Coffee/quick lunch break	30	
10:30	Group work	Work in subgroups mixing SUPPORTER partners, focusing on selected grounding actions in the realm of organisational culture & awareness-raising, and GBV 1) Share about the main challenges to successful implementation of the selected actions 2) Possible solutions	30 min	Three groups, Miro board Facilitation: Maxime, Nathalie Selected partners' grounded actions GA3 LSU GA5 BL GA1 CA (...)
11:00	Plenary	Feedback from subgroups: Report about main implementation challenges and encountered solution.	10 min	Feedback in plenary Lessons learnt for implementation Maxime Group facilitators to provide feedback (SS, KG, SL)
11:10	Group work	Group work: connecting the dots and setting up priorities. The sequence will focus on: 1) how to connect the different grounding actions relating to GBV for a successful implementation? 2) what else is necessary to build a comprehensive policy on addressing gender-based violence? Next move?	30 min	Facilitation: Maxime, Nathalie Same group as before and keeping the focus on specific grounding actions

11:40	Plenary	Feedback from subgroup: each group to come up with set priorities IOs to prepare to 'report' in plenary	15 min	IOS: report on one next step each. Recommendations from trainers about priority setting and a holistic view. Maxime and Nathalie
11:55	Wrap-up	Exit questionnaire What's next	5 min	Eugenia

Script 2c: Intermediate training on gender equality and inclusive and progressive GEPs: focus setting up a GEP – 30 May 2024

In this session we will use the findings of the initial analysis (session 1 and session 2) and the work done by the IOs to identify the areas of intervention to be addressed in your Gender Equality Plan. Not all areas can be tackled at the same time, and some may be more pressing than others. The training addresses: Identification of institutional gender equality plan objectives, setting targets and measures to remedy the identified problems, allocating resources and responsibilities, and defining timelines. The priorities set out for an organisation will depend on the available resources – mapped in T2.3.

Preparations by IOS:

- Refine your implementation plan for two grounding action to make them impactful.
- Define Indicators.
- Please send it to the core team by 21 May 2024

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
09:00	Welcome and introduction	Introduction to SUPPORTER training, including how this training connects to roadmaps & (the need for) grounded actions on data + relation to ML	5 min	Welcome Recording and photo consent ESF: Eugenia
09:05	Lecture	The possibilities of sports to make a difference in GBV in sport higher education	30 min	Tine Vertommen
09:35	Q&A		15 min	Tine Vertommen
09:50	Lecture	Indicators as monitoring and evaluation of GEPS: what, why and how? Gear Tool and steps (monitoring and evaluation)	20 min	How to formulate, ideal types, examples of IOs Nathalie Wuiame, UGOT
10:10	Q&A		10 min	Nathalie Wuiame
10:20	Break		30 min	
10:50	Re-cap of where we are and want to achieve	Re-cap of Tines presentation. Take home messages. Instructions	5 min	Nathalie Wuiame
10:55	Exercise I	<i>Group work: Work on grounding action to refine your indicator regarding monitoring</i>	20 min	Work on grounding actions to refine the indicators Small groups of two IOs

				Facilitators join the groups to support
11:15		<i>Plenary</i>		Feedback: trainer picks up on some good examples
11:20	Instruction		5 min	
11:25	Exercise	<i>Group work: Work on grounding action to refine your indicator regarding evaluation</i>	20 min	
11:45	Recap		10 min	Recommendations from trainers
11:55	Wrap up	Instructions for what to do next, considering the results of the exercise Exit questionnaire, next steps, tasks for IOS	5 min	ESF Include what to take from here into the mutual learning

MODULE III: Advanced training on gender+ equality and 4I-GEPs

This third and final module is an advanced training on gender+ equality and 4I-GEPs in the sports environment. It builds on the first two modules of trainings and mutual learning, and work carried out by the IOs T2.1 and T2.3. The focus of the training is the fourth, fifth and sixth steps of the gender equality plan, implementation, monitoring & evaluation, and what happens after the gender equality plan – the training will focus on what the IOs have done. Key concepts are reviewed and the concepts of intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful in relation to GEPs are explored in detail by both discussing the theory and providing actual examples.

It consists of three ½ day online sessions (1-1,5 hours before lunch, 2 hours after lunch) ML workshop is in M24.

- Designing a gender equality plan (GEP):
- Key components of a GEP
- Dealing with resistances and challenges to gender+ equality and GEP implementation
- Supporting gender equality change agent

Content

Session 1: Implementing a gender equality plan (step 4)

Session 2: Results of the monitoring and evaluation of gender equality plan measures (step 5)

Session 3: What comes after the gender equality plan (step 6)

Ideal target group

- GEP teams/team members
- IOs institutional members directly involved in driving institutional change processes

Materials

- D2.1, D2.2, D3.1
- Appendix 2
- IOs Roadmaps
- UniSAFE Assessment Framework (D6.2)

Script 3a: Advanced training on 4I-GEPs 31 January 2025

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
9:00	Introduction	Brief presentation of the concept of these three sessions Introducing our keynote speaker	10 min	PPT
9:10-9.40	Intersectionality in sports	Keynote speech - Focus on intersectionality. Sex and socio-economic, cultural factors	40 min	Anne Schmitt, associate professor, Paris- Saclay Focus on intersectionality. Sex and socio-economic, cultural factors Example of girls in sailing schools in California and France?
9:40 - 10:00	Q&A			Nathalie
10:00-10:30	IOs on intersectionality in practice	What is your reaction to these stories? Have you ever had some cases like those? How would you deal with such situation in your IOs? What, if anything, is missing in your current policy framework in order to deal with such cases?	30 min	Preparation of personas in an online document. Work in sub-groups on personas. Two personas per groups.
10:30-11:00	Sharing group work in plenary	Feedback and Q&A	30 min	
11:00	Break		20 min	
11:20	Gender-based violence and intersectionality	Presentation of results of the UniSAFE and work on GBV and intersectionality	20 min	Sofia Draw on the work done by UGOT for GenderSAFE
11:40	Feedback and Q&A		10 min	
11:50-12.10	Implementation of the GEP	Monitoring intersectionality	20 min	Presentation of monitoring indicators including intersectionality Suzanne
12.10-12.30		How do you monitor intersectionality in your current GEP? What can you improve?	20 min	IOs reflect individually on a google doc
12.30-12.50		Plenary		Sharing reflection

12:50		Next steps, preparations required, dates etc.	10 min	Prepare & launch exit questionnaire;
13:00	End			

Script 3b: Advanced training on 4I-GEPs; 20 February 2025

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
9:00		Welcome and introductions	10 min	PPT
9.10	Innovation in sport	Keynote speech: Unisex sports and their potential to strengthen equality in sport. CU	40 min	Irena Martinkova, CU. First topic in general, and then introduce what we are doing at the faculty, in order to introduce an implementation to the environment of sport faculties.
9.50	Q&A	Q&A	20 min	
10.10	Break		10 min	
10.20	IOs on innovative in practice	Two IOs present jointly on how they are innovative in their actions: what measures are innovative? How are they implemented, monitored & evaluated -> ending with how it will be included in 4-IGEP	40 min	4 break-out rooms "Facilitators": Nathalie, Karin, Suzanne, Sofia
11.00	Reporting in plenary	Reporting in plenary	20 min	Facilitators
11.20		What's innovative about intersectionality in gender-based violence in GEP measures?	20 min	Sofia
11:40	Break		10 min	
11:50	IOs on impactful in practice	Two IOs present jointly what measures they have taken to ensure impact? How are these implemented, monitored & evaluated -> ending with how it will be included in 4-IGEP	40 min	4 break-out rooms "Facilitators": Nathalie, Karin, Suzanne, Sofia
12:30	Reporting back	Reporting back in plenary	10 min	
12:40		Next steps, preparations required, dates etc.	10 min	Prepare & launch exit questionnaire;
12:50	End			

Script 3c: Advanced training on 4I-GEPs: 5 March 2025

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
9:00		Welcome and introductions Recap of questionnaire	10 min	UGOT - Nathalie
9.10	What's next – what comes after the GEP?	Inspiring presentation, Q&A and participatory exercise	90 min	Ayse Gül

10:40	Break		20 min	
11:00		Introduction/presentation of key resistances according to our survey, and other work (GS/ML); with a focus on what to expect next, after the GEP?	20	UGOT - Sofia
11:20	Exercise	Exercise on resistance, with scenarios, identifying 'solutions', ways of working around R. Realise: Is this a situation you've met? Reflect: How did it effect you? Respond: What could've been done to avoid; what can you do in advance to avoid this in your organisation?	20	Preparation of scenarios of resistance GenderSAFE UGOT – Nathalie Four groups, four scenarios
12:00	Sharing in plenary		20 min	UGOT – Nathalie
12:20	Next steps, preparations required, dates etc.			Next steps – SEERC ESF – Prepare & launch exit questionnaire
12:30	end			

APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: GUIDING PRINCIPLES FOR INSTITUTIONAL CHANGE

PROMOTING GENDER EQUALITY THROUGH INSTITUTIONAL CHANGE

Guiding principles

To be effective and to bring about real and long-lasting transformation towards gender equality, institutional change should be:

Participatory, as stakeholders' mobilisation is better achieved through their direct participation in the process of change. Participatory techniques can support the implementation of this guiding principle. Participation also means that devised measures and actions are drawing upon the experience of future change agents.

Holistic, as it should encompass in a common, structured and articulated vision all the issues relevant to gender equality and gender mainstreaming in the institution. Experience shows that tackling these issues in isolation from each other can hardly bring about real institutional change. One of the reasons is that a holistic view offers a more comprehensive perspective on the role of institutions in reproducing gender inequalities, while a narrower perspective tends to emphasise only the individual level of change.

Inclusive, in terms of the range of stakeholders involved, the thematic issues covered, as well as of the approach to gender+ inequalities. Inclusiveness is key to tackle situations of multiple discrimination, to involve different categories of staff or users (including students) in the process of change, and to strengthen ownership around this process.

Visible, because accountability to ascribed objectives matters. Accountability, which can be multi-level (towards the institution and its staff, towards peer institutions, funding organisations or external legal bodies), is stronger if commitments taken to mainstream gender equality and a gender perspective in research are made public and visible.

Flexible, because both individuals and institutions are learning by doing. Moreover, the objectives, measures and actions should be continuously adapted to current realities as new or emerging issues (which had not been contemplated when planning actions) should be taken into account (either when they are brought by stakeholders or evidenced by collected data). Besides, institutional change should be flexible with regards to measurable impact so as to privilege effectiveness.

Sustainable, as institutional change necessarily takes time, which requires actions and initiatives towards gender equality to rely upon sufficient resources and to be incorporated into strategic documents, policies, schemes and 'ways of doing things', so that changes can pervade the regular functioning of the institution.

Source: GE ACADEMY - Yellow Window

https://ge-academy.eu/ge-uploads/2022/11/Handout-1_Guiding-principles.pdf

APPENDIX 2: ROADMAP TO GENDER EQUALITY PLANS IN RESEARCH AND HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS – A SHORT GUIDE

According to the European Commission Communication on ‘A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth’ (COM(2012) 392 final),

A Gender Equality Plan is defined as a set of actions aiming at:

- conducting impact assessment / audits of procedures and practices to identify gender bias.
- implementing innovative strategies to correct any bias.
- setting targets and monitoring progress via indicators.

A Gender Equality Plan is more than a commitment to gender equality. It includes an analysis and bases its actions upon the findings of an assessment of gender (in)equality and gender bias within an organisation. Similarly, a Gender Equality Plan does not only consist of a series of objectives and targets, but also comprises of a set of practical measures, whose implementation should be monitored and evaluated. This set of actions, which can have different targets and degrees of complexity, is meant to address the contextual features of the organisations and to articulate a strategic view aimed at achieving gender equality.

This short guide presents the six main steps to develop a Gender Equality Plan:

Step 1: Getting started

Are you ready for setting up a Gender Equality Plan in your organisation?

- **Remember that context matters:** rather than simply copying successful actions or approaches that others did, ask which actions would work best in your own institution, considering its objectives and relevant regional/national contexts.
- **Find support:** involve gender experts, potential allies at different levels within and outside the institution, and investigate possible funding opportunities for the gender equality work **that needs to be undertaken**.

Step 2: Analysing and assessing the state-of-play in the institution

The assessment of the state-of-play of the institution will provide insight on which measures need to be implemented. The comprehensiveness of this initial analysis will depend on the available resources. A standard approach would include:

- Analysing sex-disaggregated data about staff and students. Data broken down by sex is needed to detect any gender differences and to identify the most pressing areas requiring intervention. The first step is to check which data are readily available. If data do not yet exist in your organisation, efforts to collect such data need to be made. The second step is to carry out a gender analysis based on the collected data.
- Identifying the existing measures promoting gender equality. The implementation and results of existing measures (such as those to promote women’s careers, to raise awareness about gender equality, or to enhance work-life balance) need to be critically assessed, together with those involved, seeking how their effectiveness can be enhanced.
- Reviewing relevant legislation and policies in your country. This allows for understanding where the organisation stands, the identification of any possible breaches and for providing the rationale to support gender equality actions. This knowledge can also support some of the measures within the Gender Equality Plan.

Step 3: Setting up a Gender Equality Plan

The findings of the initial analysis allow identifying the areas of intervention to be addressed in a Gender Equality Plan. Not all areas can however be tackled at the same time, and some may be more pressing than others. The priorities set out for an organisation will depend on the available resources.

A Gender Equality Plan needs to be holistic and integrated. This means that the identified areas of intervention are interdependent. The Gender Equality Plan needs to address a variety of issues relevant for the whole community and organisational system. The basic actions to be taken into consideration in the process of setting up a Gender Equality Plan include:

- Get inspiration from measures implemented by other organisations, but make sure to adapt these measures considering the specificities of your own context.
- Define SMART objectives and measures for your Gender Equality Plan (i.e. Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic and Time-related).
- Define the timeframe of the Gender Equality Plan, as well as a realistic timeline for its implementation. Do not forget to establish specific monitoring periods to report on the progress achieved.
- Promote the participation of actors of all levels when defining measures and actions of the Gender Equality Plan. A participatory approach will help define meaningful measures to the actors involved and will enhance their willingness to implement the measures in the Gender Equality Plan.
- Identify and utilise existing resources when planning the measures. Building on existing resources has the advantage of promoting the institutionalisation of gender-sensitive and/or gender-specific procedures or activities.
- Agree on clear staff responsibilities for each measure. The Gender Equality Plan should clearly indicate ‘who is responsible for what and when’.
- Build alliances. The measures in a Gender Equality Plan will not deliver or be achieved unless the Plan is supported by stakeholders at all levels. Take time to explain what the Gender Equality Plan implies for all targeted stakeholders. These efforts need to be continued throughout the implementation of the Gender Equality Plan.
- Think about sustainability. The resources to promote gender equality through institutional change are not unlimited and neither is the duration of your Gender Equality Plan. To ensure the sustainability of gender equality actions, it is important to embed practices in the normal routines, policies and procedures of the organisation.

4. Step 4: Implementing a Gender Equality Plan

Having set up the Gender Equality Plan, it is time to start implementing it:

- Put the measures of the Gender Equality Plan in motion according to the defined timeline.
- Try to embed and institutionalise as many measures/actions as possible in order to ensure their sustainability.
- Organise regular meetings with the team responsible for the implementation of the Gender Equality Plan.
- These meetings are not only important to design and plan activities in a participatory way, but also to discuss the progress, main achievements and aspects that can be improved. The regular meetings will also help to identify any possible challenges or problems and act upon them.
- Plan meetings with senior management and leadership, human resources staff, and/or other co-workers you consider relevant. This will help create ownership of the Gender Equality Plan, motivate the staff involved, strengthen the potential of the Plan, and maximise the impact of the Plan’s actions.
- Continue engaging stakeholders on an on-going basis and do not forget to keep in touch with stakeholders you engaged in a previous phase.
- Give visibility to the Gender Equality Plan. Inform your institution about the existence of the Gender Equality Plan. Use different channels and routes to communicate the Plan, its main areas of interventions, timeframe and achievements.
- Be aware that adaptations to the Plan may be needed. A Gender Equality Plan is not static or immutable. Several circumstances may require modifications or amendments to the Plan. Discuss with the implementation team and with senior management and leadership whether and how the Plan can be adapted.

- Seek to understand why some measures are not being (fully) implemented and make adjustments as needed. Keep up-to-date with innovative actions in other institutions.
- Be prepared to face obstacles or resistances when implementing some measures and act upon them

Step 5: Monitoring progress and evaluating a Gender Equality Plan

Monitoring and evaluation instruments support effective actions and accountability. Establish indicators, targets and follow-up instruments, while also allocating resources, to assess actions and to enhance the knowledge about on-going implementation. Gender expertise (possibly external) may need to be considered in monitoring and evaluation processes, potentially along with other expertise on change dynamics or other specific issues tackled by the Gender Equality Plan.

Monitoring is crucial to:

- Enable seeing where and how actions are being implemented.
- Help identify and address potential sources of resistance to change.
- Indicate whether a transformative dynamic exists.

Indicators should be implementation-oriented, and adapted to the purposes of the action. Monitoring does not mean looking only at figures and data; other underlying, qualitative aspects also need to be considered.

Evaluation is key to sustainability and further enhancement because it:

- Provides evidence of actual changes or lack thereof.
- Highlights the positive dynamics and opportunities brought by gender mainstreaming strategies.
- Is an opportunity to enhance the support to gender equality policies?
- Paves the way for future, even more resolute actions, and offers a valuable knowledge for their design.

Transforming complex organisations, challenging processes, routines and power relations among staff takes time. Attention must be paid to short-term and mid-term milestones and potential achievements as well.

A thorough, context-sensitive and mixed evaluation approach helps your strategy to make a substantial difference.

Step 6. What comes after the Gender Equality Plan?

A Gender Equality Plan will conclude at some point in time. However, this is not 'the end' towards promoting gender equality. A new cycle should start. It is likely that the sustainability of some measures and procedures is already ensured, whereas others may still require further action, or new areas of attention may have been identified. This is the point where a decision needs to be made on how to continue the efforts undertaken so far and what any new Gender Equality Plan should address.

ON THIS ROADMAP

The information gathered in this roadmap was developed in cooperation with the European Commission, Directorate-General Research and Innovation in 2016. Based on national initiatives and projects funded by the EU Framework Programmes for Research and Technological Development, and in consultation with experts and stakeholders, an online tool was designed to assist research and higher education institutions in setting up, implementing, monitoring and evaluating gender equality plans. The most important tips of the step-by-step guide available in the online tool have been summarised in this roadmap.

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Examples of quantitative indicators

Quantitative indicators are relevant whenever they are adapted to the expected results of the planned actions. Quantitative indicators most often include:

- the number of female and male candidates for positions.
- the number of women and men in selection panels (for recruitment and promotion).
- horizontal sex segregation in respective categories of occupation.
- the number of male and female individuals targeted and reached by gender awareness-raising or planned training actions.
- gender ratios in accessing research grants (and other resources, e.g. laboratory spaces or personnel).
- the gender pay gap among different categories of staff, including researchers.

Examples of qualitative indicators

Qualitative indicators can contribute to a better understanding of the process of change. They may bring evidence of change and that gender equality and awareness are gaining ground. Qualitative indicators have also a stronger learning potential. They support self-reflexivity and may provide indications for a continuous enhancement of the implemented actions. The following dimensions can be considered when defining/assessing qualitative indicators:

- The uptake of the gender equality objectives set by the Gender Equality Plan by different categories of stakeholders.
- The actual transformation towards greater gender-sensitivity of both formal and informal practices as an effect of implemented actions, notably in the areas of human resources management, decision-making, evaluation and governance.

APPENDIX 3: ROADMAP TO GENDER EQUALITY PLANS IN RESEARCH AND HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS – SUCCESS FACTORS AND COMMON OBSTACLES

Success factors for promoting gender equality through institutional change

In the past number of years, key elements that appear to support gender equality work in research and higher education institutions have been identified. When these elements are present in research and higher education institutions, efforts towards gender equality are more likely to succeed and to contribute to effective change. The following success factors can help promote gender equality through institutional change in research and higher education settings.

These success factors can also be understood as ‘basic requirements’ to ensure that gender equality actions are more resilient and impactful. Furthermore, the presence of these basic requirements may help avoid and/or overcome common obstacles that are encountered when carrying out gender equality work in research and higher education institutions.

1. Leadership and senior management support:

- Endorse initiatives promoting gender equality.
- Counter opposition/resistance to initiatives promoting gender equality.
- Facilitate the mobilisation and availability of human and financial resources within the institution.
- Ensure the sustainability of actions.

2. A well-equipped and well-located ‘gender equality body’ (e.g. a dedicated unit, working group, team, or office):

- Coordinates and monitors gender equality efforts.
- Ensures the implementation of gender equality actions with the support of and in cooperation with leadership and executive bodies (e.g. human resources department).
- Ensures that human resources, knowledge and expertise are available in-house.

3. Involvement of different categories of stakeholders (inside and outside the institution):

- Allows the combination of different expertise and types of knowledge.
- Creates a feeling of ownership for gender equality actions implementation.
- Reduces opposition/resistance to initiatives promoting gender equality.
- Guarantees that tasks and responsibilities are shared.
- Allows for reaching different organisational and/or disciplinary staff and departments.
- Increases the commitment and potential impact of gender equality measures.
- Helps achieve sustainable changes institution wide.
- Ensures that the process is more transparent inside and

4. Embedding into existing structures and management procedures:

- Ensures institutional change towards gender equality and strengthens the sustainability of planned measures.
- Guarantees that gender-sensitive and gender-specific actions are incorporated into standard management procedures (e.g. gender training, gender-sensitive recruitment and career management procedures, collection of sex-disaggregated data).

5. Availability of sex-disaggregated data:

- Allows a gender diagnosis of the institution for each category and level of staff and students.
- Helps design evidence-based and effective measures to address any identified problems.
- Allows monitoring of achievements and progress.

6. Setting clear targets and practical objectives:

- Proves commitment to implement the planned gender equality actions.
- Allows the assessment of progress and makes the Gender Equality Plan more concrete and tangible.

- Allows for definition of responsibilities within the institution.

7. Developing competences:

- Enhances knowledge and its transfer among different staff and employees within the institution.
- Ensures a common understanding of what promoting gender equality through institutional change implies.

8. Monitoring and evaluation practices:

- Increase the robustness and sustainability of gender mainstreaming strategies.
- Allow for drawing upon lessons learnt from implemented initiatives.
- Provide visibility, enable measuring actual progress and help identify areas for further improvement.

9. Flexibility and resilience:

- Allow for the reassessment of gender-specific priorities for the institution at different levels.
- Allow for the adaptation and reshaping of gender equality measures, in cooperation with (the growing circles of) stakeholders, based on insights and/or data in order to ensure that targets and objectives are achieved

Common obstacles and how to overcome them

Obstacles to set up, implement, monitor and evaluate a Gender Equality Plan are diverse and frequent. Some examples of obstacles and suggestions on how to overcome them are provided below.

Resistance to gender equality initiatives can be observed both at the individual and at the institutional level, and can take many forms (both explicit and implicit). Overcoming resistance can be challenging, but not impossible:

- Consider setting up awareness-raising training tailored to different staff.
- Ensure explicit and visible commitment from leadership and senior management.
- Involve key actors in identifying problems and resistance points so that solutions can be devised together, and create a feeling of ownership of these solutions.

An absence of dedicated, adequate and sustained resources, both human and financial, for gender equality work and for developing, implementing and monitoring Gender Equality Plans is a common obstacle. Some tips to help overcome this obstacle are:

- Clearly outline the value and the concrete results of gender equality actions (such as increased staff retention, more robust research, more diversity in staff).
- Search for human and financial resources at national, regional or institutional level in the early stages of the development of a Gender Equality Plan.

The lack of institutional or organisational authority can undermine gender equality initiatives. The staff involved in the development and roll-out of a Gender Equality Plan may not hold the authority or decision-making powers to promote and drive change in the institution. This can lead to frustration, limited progress and blockages in terms of achievements of the Plan. This obstacle can generally be resolved by:

- Ensuring an early involvement, commitment and visible on-going support from leaders.
- Identify in the Gender Equality Plan where lies the responsibility to take decisions and liaise with these actors throughout the process.

Some individuals may strongly adhere to the belief that a commitment to academic excellence or promotion on merit alone is at odd with initiatives promoting gender equality. This belief appears to have led to an absence of women in many fields and at higher levels of academia and research settings. There are several ways to address this argument:

- Provide and promote unconscious bias training for all staff within the organisation.
- Refer to international and European research, reports and projects to show that excellence in research is based on the diversity of expertise, experience and staff, and to find evidence to support

your arguments. Check, for instance, the European Commission's She Figures, or websites of EU-funded projects such as Gendered Innovations or GenPort for inspiration.

In some countries or regions, there may be limited autonomy for (public) institutions to enable changes related to gender equality (e.g. in relation to hiring, recruitment and promotion procedures and regulations). The following actions can nevertheless be undertaken:

- Check if there is any lack of compliance with the principles of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment, as set by Directive 2006/54/EC.
- Check whether there are European, national or regional (non-)binding regulations that promote gender equality in research and/or higher education and use them as convincing arguments to enact change.
- Involve different actors to help create solutions, put actions into motion and convince senior management and leadership.

A fundamental lack of understanding of the need for and importance of gender equality may be encountered. This can lead to lack of engagement and involvement of key actors. To prevent and counteract such situation it is important to:

- Clearly reiterate that gender equality is not a 'minority' or 'women's' issue, but concerns everyone working in the institution.
- Frame gender equality as a key element to develop a successful, inclusive, open and forward-thinking research and higher education institution.
- Give visibility to gender equality by setting up a Gender Equality Plan and ensure that it is fully and publicly supported by leaders and senior managers.
- Set up (possibly mandatory) training on gender equality, in person or online, for all staff in order to ensure a shared understanding of its importance and benefits.
- Make the institution aware of gender imbalances and inequalities, as well as gender equality achievements, by regularly publishing sex-disaggregated data.

A lack of availability, or access to, sex-disaggregated human resources data is a challenge. These data are required to develop a baseline or initial assessment of where gender equality actions need to be targeted, to help counter resistance with actual up-to-date facts and figures, and to monitor progress. The following actions can be considered to make sex-disaggregated data available:

- Update existing human resources data collection and management systems to enable statistics broken down by sex (and other intersectional variables, such as age).
- Allocate resources (time and budget) for collecting and analysing data (e.g. as a measure of a Gender Equality Plan).
- Store any resultant data in a way that complies with European and national data protection requirements.

Not engaging potential key allies and/or actors early in the Gender Equality Plan process can seriously limit results. Therefore, it is important to:

Recruit allies and enablers of gender equality work early in the process.

Ensuring the sustainability and resilience of gains related to gender equality can be challenging. Change of leadership, budget cutbacks, or apathy can lead to reduced or limited sustainability of a Gender Equality Plan. To overcome this obstacle, it is necessary to:

- Deliver training, workshops, seminars, meetings etc. to staff not directly involved in drafting or rolling out the Gender Equality Plan, because their support is important to progress and avoid obstacles during the implementation of the Plan.
- Frame the Gender Equality Plan as an encompassing, institutional plan so that a greater cross-departmental and • faculty support is ensured.

Some research and higher education institutions may not have had a previous history or tradition of teaching or engaging with gender studies. This can mean that it is more challenging to convince staff of the importance and benefits of gender equality work and Gender Equality Plans. This obstacle may require to:

- Look for support from and utilise gender equality networks (at a national, regional or international level).
- Make use of such networks and gender expertise to enhance institutional competence and knowledge.
- Check Eurogender's Stakeholders Directory to find gender experts and trainers in your country or GenPort's People directory to find, among others, gender networks, and gender equality practitioners and advisers.

Embed a commitment to both gender equality and the work related to the Gender Equality Plan into multiple organisational structures. This means that support, buy-in and commitment for the Plan will need to be sought from multiple stakeholders and not only allocated to a specific school or department.

- Allocate gender equality work to a specific multi-annual budget.
 - Create and implement regular accountability, monitoring and evaluation structures, and/or tools into a Gender Equality Plan to flag when sustainability begins to lag and to indicate actions needed prior to crisis points being reached.
- Want to know more?

Visit GEAR, EIGE's online tool about Gender Equality in Academia and Research:

www.eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/tools-methods/GEAR

ABOUT EIGE

The European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) is the EU knowledge centre on gender equality. EIGE supports policy-makers and all relevant institutions in their efforts to make equality between women and men a reality for all Europeans and beyond by providing them with specific expertise and comparable and reliable data on gender equality in Europe. More information: <http://www.eige.europa.eu>

ON THIS PUBLICATION

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Annex 2 – Agendas of Mutual Learning Programme Workshops and Sessions

**Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with
Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive
Gender Equality Plans**

SUPPORTER Mutual Learning Programme

SEERC

Author: SEERC

First draft: 05.09.2023

Introduction

This document outlines the design of the SUPPORTER Mutual Learning Programme, which focuses on the implementation of the mutual learning scheme developed in T3.1. It consists of:

- three Mutual Learning Workshops which will follow the WP2 training modules
- Bilateral ML meetings among IOs
- IOs Learning Diaries

Mutual Learning Workshops

Mutual Learning Workshop I: Introduction to the Mutual Learning Programme

Objectives

The first Mutual Learning Workshop (MLW) has the following objectives:

- Introduce the Mutual Learning Programme (Mutual Learning Workshops, Bilateral Meetings and Learning Diaries)
- Provide IOs with the opportunity to discuss and reflect on the knowledge acquired through the first training module
- Introduce the reflexive self-assessment (guidance document and template)

Target audience

- Gender Equality officers/Diversity, Equality and Inclusion officers
- GEP teams/team members (people involved in gender equality plans on a regular basis e.g. Chairs or Members of committees)
- Human resources officers
- Senior and middle managers

Activities and Methodologies

- Discussions: IOs will engage in discussions reflecting on the knowledge acquired in the first training module as well as their national and institutional practices. Discussions will be facilitated and guided by core team members.
- World Café: participants will be divided into 5 groups consisting of 4 members and 1 facilitator and will be provided with three questions (one for each round) resulting from the issues discussed in the first training module (i.e. basic training on key concepts, institutional change, gender equality and Gender Equality Plans). One IOs member should act as a rapporteur for each group.
- Presentations: Core team members will present the mapping results, the components of the Mutual Learning Programme, and the self-reflexive assessment.

Expected Outcomes

- IOs will develop a thorough understanding of the Mutual Learning Programme, its individual components, steps to follow (i.e. Bilateral Meetings and Learning Diaries) and actions to be taken.
- IOs will reflect on the knowledge acquired through the first training module and will utilize it to pursue institutional change in their organisations.
- IOs will be fully informed about the self-reflexive assessment of T2.3.

Detailed Agenda for MLW I

Thursday, September 14th					
Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations	Presenter/Facilitator
14:00	Introduction to the Mutual Learning Programme	Introduction to the MLP	5 min	PPT and templates	SEERC
		What are your expectations?	10 min	Mentimeter/Slido	
		MLW, Bilateral meetings and Learning Diaries, MMS	25 min		
		Q&A	5 min		
14.45	Break		15 min		
15:00	Reflection on national and institutional frameworks	IOs will briefly refer to their national and institutional policies regarding Gender Equality	40 min	Orally	IOs members
		D2.1 mapping results	15 min	PPT	UGOT (Sofia)
		Discussion	30 min		SEERC
		End of day I closing remarks	5 min		SEERC
16:30	End of Day I				
Friday, September 15th					
9:00	Welcome/Coffee time				
9:30	Reflection on Training Module I	Introduction to World Café	5 min	World Café format	Facilitators: SEERC (Faye, Zoi)
		Five rounds (Each table discusses a	75 min	5 groups (4 persons + 1 facilitator)	ESF (Eugenia) UGOT (Karin, Suzanne)

		question resulting from the first training module)	40 min	5 rounds (15 min)	
		Harvest			
11:30	Break				
11:45	Introduction to reflexive self-assessment	Introduction to reflexive assessment	30 min	PPT	ESF (Eugenia)
12:15	Conclusion	Concluding remarks	30 min	PPT	SEERC
		Key takeaways from the ML Workshop			
12:45	End				

Second Mutual Learning Workshop Agenda

June 13-14, 2024

CITY College, University of York EUROPE Campus, Thessaloniki

Intersectionality in the roadmap implementation

Objectives

The in-person Mutual Learning Workshop in Thessaloniki focuses on three main objectives:

1. Integrating an intersectional approach to the implementation of the institutional roadmaps and the development of Gender Equality Plans
2. Exploring how the values and principles of sports can contribute to the promotion of gender equality in the academic environment and in the society in general
3. Collecting insights and supporting the effective implementation of the institutional roadmaps.

These objectives are pursued through:

- Group exercises on the topics discussed in Training Module II around data collection, and monitoring and evaluation
- An open discussion on the positive vision of sports
- A three-level reflection on the first months of the roadmap implementation:
 - a) Via a bilateral discussion with another IO

- b) Via a review of the learning diary input with the mentoring team
- c) Through an exchange of encountered challenges and promising practices with the consortium

Expected Outcomes

- Align perceptions among participants regarding key concepts from Training Module II, ensuring a uniform understanding across the consortium.
- Achieve a deepened understanding of intersectionality and how it can be integrated into data collection and the development of institutional policies.
- Facilitate an exchange of insights on challenges and successful endeavours among the implementing organisations, supporting the effective implementation of institutional roadmaps.
- Reflect on the lessons learnt from planning and implementing the first Grounding Actions and consider necessary adjustments based on these insights
- Stimulate discussion on the potential of sports education to act as a catalyst for spreading the values of fairness and equity, together with gender equality, within academic settings and in the society

Guidelines for IOs' preparation

- Read thoroughly the definition of intersectionality: An intersectional GEP considers gender in relation to its intersections with other sociocultural, economic and political inequalities such as **race, ethnicity, class, sexuality, age, disability, nationality** and so on, and proposes actions which take into account how different forms of inequality and disadvantage interconnect.
Example 1: Although the University provides scholarships to ethnic minorities, such as Roma, and refugees, a high rate of dropouts from refugee and Roma female students has been observed. When asked, the students mentioned 'not feeling included by staff and peers' as the reason for the dropout.
Example 2: During the selection process for an academic position among candidates with the same qualifications, female applicants who wear a headscarf in their CV photo have fewer chances of being called to the interview stage compared to those without any indications of religious practice in their photos.
- In your roadmaps, you have stated that specific Grounding Actions address intersectionality (Table 3 of your roadmap). Please think of the following:
 - Name **three intersecting inequalities** that will be covered in your roadmap in these Grounding Actions, or later in your new GEP (e.g. gender with religion, as in a Muslim female academic, or gender with nationality/origin, as in refugee female students). If you have not identified any already, please do so in order to discuss them in the workshop.
 - How and why are these intersecting inequalities relevant to your institution?
 - Do you collect relevant data from the different groups within your institution?
 - What kind of monitoring indicators would you need to monitor and evaluate progress regarding these intersecting inequalities within your institution?
- It is a fact that Sports contain the element of competition, largely remain male dominated, and they are predominantly binary. Still, we should not forget that Sports are also based on the gentle notion of Fair Play, which can take a new enhanced meaning if we infuse it with the principles of Gender Equality and intersectionality. Through this lens, think of how we can project a positive vision by focusing on how sports can contribute to gender equality in the society.
- **About the Monitoring & Mentoring Meetings:** Revisit your learning diary and think of all the activities you have carried out so far in the framework of your roadmap implementation. Be

prepared to present your learning diary and share your results, thoughts and next steps with your mentor.

Regarding your ongoing awareness-raising GA, think of the following:

- What is your progress so far? What steps/activities have you already started/implemented?
 - Have you decided on the exact type of events that you will hold? (e.g. internal/external, workshops/webinars/lectures)
 - Have you started planning your local stakeholder event? Which stakeholders have you invited/plan to invite?
 - Have you decided on the exact topics that you will touch upon in your events?
 - Have you invited speakers? Have you set a date for the event?
 - Have you devised a communication plan to engage stakeholders for your local stakeholder event?
 - Will your events be stand-alone or part of other activities that you have planned at institutional/faculty level (e.g. an annual campaign on combatting violence at higher education institutions)
 - How can we support you in organising and implementing your local stakeholder event?
- **About the Bilateral Meetings:** You will be paired with another organisation to have a bilateral discussion on your roadmaps and exchange experiences. Focus on your ongoing Grounding Actions, especially on the awareness-raising Grounding Action that you are currently implementing and discuss the following:
 - Have you encountered any challenges and how did you manage them?
 - Did you develop any good practices that you would like to share?
 - Now that you have been implementing these Grounding Actions for a few months, do you think that it would benefit from any changes that would make it more feasible or effective?
 In the second day of the workshop, you will need to present to the plenary the encountered challenges and inspiring practices of your pair organisation! So, make sure to keep notes!

Agenda Day I – June 13th

Time	Programme	Approach	Observations
09:00	Welcome coffee		
09:30	Introduction		SEERC (Faye)
09:45 – 10.05	Thinking of intersectionality in institutional change in the academic environment	Presentation of intersectionality as the theme of the workshop - and why it is important, how the IOs can benefit from integrating into their GEPs; what problem will this solve?	UGOT (Nathalie)
10.05 – 10.15	Reflections on Training Module II, Session I on data collection	Summary of training's key points	UGOT (Nathalie)
10.15 – 11.45	Exercise on intersecting inequalities in the implementing organisations	<p>Exercise on integrating the identified intersections into the roadmaps or GEPs</p> <p>Work in plenary using post-its, markers and a board</p>	<p>ESF (Eugenia & Ildi)</p> <p>IOs will be asked to write down the pre-identified intersections and justify why they have chosen them. Similarly with the GAs. Then an intersection will be chosen and together we will work with an example of data collection (missing data, collecting sensitive data, challenges, what will intersectional data collection solve in their institutions etc.)</p> <p>IOs will be asked in advance to a) identify at least 3 intersections in their institutions, b) identify those GAs in their roadmaps</p>

			which have been labelled as intersectional and c) consider how they can integrate the three intersections into their GEPs.
11.45	Coffee break		
12.00 - 12.10	Reflections on Training Module II, Session II on strategic framing and monitoring indicators	Summary of training's key points	UGOT (Nathalie)
12.10 – 13.00	Embedding intersectionality in strategic framing/monitoring indicators	Breakout groups exercise	SEERC/UGOT/ESF
13:00	Lunch break		
14.00 – 15.15	Bilateral Meetings (BLs) and Mentoring & Monitoring Meetings (M&Ms) I	<p>Suggested agenda for the BLs to be sent to partners</p> <p>M&Ms will focus on the learning diaries</p>	<p>BLs:</p> <p>UNIBL-NSA: Group study room, Library (6th floor)</p> <p>GSTUPES-SUPES (Nathalie): Working room, Library (6th floor)</p> <p>M&Ms:</p> <p>LSU (Faye): Conference room (8th floor)</p> <p>CU (Zoi): Conference room (7th floor)</p> <p>UL (ESF): Project room, Library (6th floor)</p> <p>UVT (ESF): MP room (5th floor)</p>
15.15	Coffee break		

15.30 – 16.45	Bilateral Meetings (BLs) and Mentoring & Monitoring Meetings (M&Ms) II	Suggested agenda for the BLs to be sent to partners M&Ms will focus on the learning diaries	BLs: LSU-UL: Group study room, Library (6 th floor) UVT-CU: Working room, Library (6 th floor) M&Ms: NSA (Faye-Nikos): Conference room (8 th floor) UNIBL (Zoi): Conference room (7 th floor) SUPES (ESF) GSTUPES (ESF)
16.45 – 17.00	Return to plenary and end of Day I	Wrap up, suggestions for short walk in the city and instructions for dinner	SEERC
Free time in Thessaloniki			
19.30	Group dinner at Mpakal		

Agenda Day II – June 14th

Time	Programme	Approach	Observations
09:00	Welcome coffee		
09:30 – 10.45	Reflection on first months of roadmap implementation	Collective input from BLs Focus on awareness raising GA	IOs, SEERC
10.45	Coffee break		
11.00 – 12.00	The role of sports in the promotion of GE in the society	Keynote lecture & discussion	Professor Ani Chroni
12.00 – 12.30	Conclusions and steps forward	Wrap up, upcoming actions/deadlines	SEERC

12.30 – 13.30	General Assembly 2 SUPPORTER General Assembly 02 AGENDA.docx	Agenda by ESF	ESF, all Hybrid to include UGOT
13.30	Lunch		

Third Mutual Learning Workshop Agenda

March 19-20, 2025

University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

From theory to practice: Drafting 4I-GEPs and policy recommendations on gender equality in sports higher education

Objectives

The in-person Mutual Learning Workshop in Ljubljana builds on Training Module III and focuses on the following objectives:

1. Explore the 4I Concepts: focus on innovation, impact, and inclusiveness.
2. Leverage roadmap insights to support the effective drafting of new institutional GEPs.
3. Collect project learnings to draft policy recommendations for advancing gender equality in sports higher education.

These objectives are pursued through:

- Interactive group exercises to deepen understanding on Training Module III topics
- A keynote speech on successful GEP implementation strategies
- Bilateral and consortium-wide discussions to share inspiring actions and lessons to avoid in new GEPs
- Comparative analysis of good practices and challenges between the first (until Thessaloniki MLW and second (until Ljubljana MLW) phases of roadmap implementation to identify improvements, declines, their causes and strategies to address them.

Expected Outcomes

- Harmonised participants' perceptions of key concepts from Training Module III
- Deepened understanding of the 4Is
- Exchange of challenges and successes among implementing organisations to improve the institutional GEP drafts and provide concrete policy recommendations

Guidelines for IOs' preparation

To prepare for our Mutual Learning Workshop in Ljubljana (19-20 March) and ensure meaningful discussions that will contribute to the development of a key project output, we kindly ask you to prepare an early draft of your new GEP.

The draft GEP needs to address the following core aspects:

1. To be **intersectional**
2. To be **inclusive**
3. To be **impactful**

4. To be **innovative**
5. To be **tailored to sports**
6. To address **gender-based violence**

a. Day 1 – 4I-GEP theory into practice

1. During the workshop, each IO will have 2 minutes to present how their new GEP will fulfil one of the 4Is (Intersectional, Innovative, Impactful, or Inclusive).
2. After these presentations, we will work in pairs to discuss the other 4Is through peer feedback and idea exchange, ensuring that all 4Is are fully embedded in each GEP.

b. Day 2 – Sustainability exercise

1. From the draft of your new 4I-GEP, select one objective/action on combatting gender-based violence, and one objective/action specifically related to sports.
2. Reflect on how you can ensure the short-term and long-term sustainability of these actions.

*Note: The terms **short-term and long-term sustainability** refer to the two roadmap phases we foresaw when co-creating the first roadmaps, described as follows:*

*- The 4I-GEP implementation period, beginning after the completion of the project and **lasting 2 years (2025-2027)**, aims at testing the implementation of the new 4I-GEP, and identifying areas of improvement.*

*- The sustainability period, **lasting 3 years (2028-2030)**, aims at revisiting the 4I-GEP in whole and enlarging its impact within and beyond the academic ecosystem.*

3. Discuss your ideas for the sustainability of these actions in breakout rooms, give and receive feedback from your peers.

4. You will have 3 min each to report back to the plenary.

Agenda Day I – March 19th

Time	Programme	Approach	Presenter
09:00	Welcome coffee		
09:30	Introduction		SEERC / UL
09:45 – 10.45	General Assembly	Agenda by ESF	ESF
10.45 – 11.15	Reflections on Training Module III (Sessions I and II?) – 4Is	Summary of training's key points	UGOT
11.15 – 11.30	Coffee break		
11.30 – 13.00	Exercise on 4Is (putting 4I-GEP theory into practice)	Breakout groups and plenary discussion	SEERC/UGOT/ESF

		- Draft GEPs	
13:00 – 14.00	Lunch break		
14.00 – 15.15	Bilateral Meetings (BLs)	Suggested agenda for the BLs to be sent to partners	IOs in pairs
15.15 – 15.30	Coffee break		
15.30 – 16.45	Comparative analysis of good practices and what is new in your GEP	Reflections from BLs in plenary Following the same structure as in the Thessaloniki MLW (post-its) Each IO reporting for their pair	IOs, SEERC
16.45 – 17.00	Conclusions and key takeaways from Day I		SEERC
17.00	End of Day I		
Free time in Ljubljana			
19.30	Group dinner		Organised by UL

Agenda Day II – March 20th

Time	Programme	Approach	Presenter/Facilitator
09:00	Welcome coffee		
09.30 – 10.20	Strategic steps for successful implementation of GEPs	Keynote lecture and discussion	Maria Sangiuliano
10.20 – 11.30	Exercise: short-term and long-term sustainability of the GEPs	Breakout groups and plenary discussion - Draft GEPs	Core team
11.30 – 11.45	Coffee break		
11.45 – 13.30	Policy recommendations – session I	TBD by UGOT	UGOT
13.30 – 14.30	Lunch break		

14.30 – 16.30	Policy recommendations session II	–	TBD by UGOT	UGOT
16.30 – 17.00	Wrap up – future steps		Q&A, presentation of upcoming activities	SEERC
17.00	End of Day II			

First Online Mutual Learning Session: Launch of the roadmap co-design process

Monday, December 11th 2023 (10:30-15:00 CET)

Objectives

The first Online ML Workshop has the following objectives:

- Facilitate a profound understanding of the co-design process – next step in the project and the related actions and timeline
- Delve into key concepts related to WP4, i.e. roadmap, grounding actions, reflection tool etc.
- Engage IOs in internal stakeholder mapping which is integral for the next step of the co-design
- Present and explain in detail the roadmap template
- Think together and consolidate the learnings from the first training module, the first mutual learning workshop and the institutional mapping completed in T2.3
- Elucidate previously discussed – but seemingly still confusing – ideas/terms to ensure that the development of the institutional roadmaps is based on uniform conceptual grounds (such as gender equality vs. gender balance, 4Is, change agents etc.)

Expected Outcomes

- A thorough understanding of the Roadmap co-design process, including the format of the roadmap, the concept and content of Grounding Actions, the timeframe and actions to be taken.
- A consolidated and harmonised understanding of key concepts
- IOs will identify the internal stakeholders who need to be involved in the co-design process through an internal stakeholder mapping exercise

Mutual Learning Session I Agenda

Monday, December 11th (10:30-15:00 CET)

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations	Presenter / Facilitator

10:30	Meeting kick-off		5 mins		Faye/Core team
10:35	Reflection on self-assessment exercise	IOs present: - Main lessons learnt from mapping - where they need to focus they attention	15 mins	Exchange	Eugenia/IOs
10:50	Key issues resulting from the self-assessment exercise	Summary of results	5 mins	PPT	Eugenia
10:55	Clarification of key concepts (e.g. gender balance vs equality, GE in different contexts, meritocracy vs GE, inherent vs systemic resistances)	1-min presentation by each IO (three IOs)	5 mins	PPT	UNIBL UL CU/ Zoi
11:00	Activity on key concepts	IOs come up with concrete examples	20 mins	Breakout rooms Groups of 4 people from different IOs plus 1 core team member	Zoi, Faye and 4 more facilitators
11:20	Break		10 mins		
11:30	Internal stakeholder mapping exercise	IOs to briefly refer to the stakeholders	30 mins	Miro	IOs Faye

		<p>they need to get started</p> <p>Naming possible stakeholders</p> <p>Who are change agents and 'resistance' agents?</p> <p>Introduction to Milestone 8</p>			
12:00	Lunch Break		60 mins		
13:00	Best practices in gender equality: the case of UGOT	Presentation of best practices from another institution	20 mins	PPT	UGOT
13:20	Introduction to Roadmaps and Co-design	<p>Introduction to Roadmaps</p> <p>Presentation of the Roadmap template</p> <p>Presentation of the co-design steps</p> <p>Expectations and challenges</p> <p>Introduction to Bilateral meetings among IOs</p> <p>Presentation of the reflection tool</p>	35 mins	PPT, roadmap template	Faye, Eugenia (presentation of reflection tool 10 mins)

13:55	Break		10 mins		
14:05	Exercise on roadmaps	Identify a grounding action on one GEP element using the reflection tool	40 mins (25 for discussion in groups and 15 for reporting)	Breakout rooms Groups of 4 people from different IOs plus 1 core team member	Exercise: Faye Zoi And 4 more members from the core team
14:45	Conclusions and Q&A		15 min		Nikos & core team
15:00	End				

Second Online Mutual Learning Session: Roadmap Implementation: Expected Challenges and Engagement of Stakeholders

Wednesday, March 20th 2024 (10:00-14:00 CET)

Objectives

The second Online Mutual Learning Workshop has the following objectives:

- Update from IOs on the institutional roadmaps
- Provide IOs with the opportunity to discuss and reflect on the expected challenges in the implementation of GAs
- Explore tools and methods for engaging further with the internal stakeholders
- Present and explain the Learning Diaries

Expected Outcomes

- Develop an in-depth understanding and prepare for challenges and resistances in the roadmap implementation process
- Reflect on the lessons learnt from the roadmap co-creation and preparation for the implementation in relation to stakeholder engagement
- Develop a solid understanding of different methods and tools to engage further with stakeholders.
- Develop a thorough understanding of the Learning Diaries and ways to utilise them

Agenda

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations	Presenter / Facilitator
10:00	Meeting kick-off and introduction		5 mins		Faye
10:05	Reflection on roadmap co-creation and implementation: engagement with internal and external stakeholders	IOs will be sent 2 questions in advance. Discussion on what worked well. Reflection on learnings and challenges.	45 mins	Breakout rooms Members from 2 IOs plus 1 core team member in each group. Report back to plenary	Faye, Eugenia, Sofia, Zoi
10:50	Engaging with stakeholders	Presentation of tools and methods to facilitate the engagement with stakeholders (e.g. surveys, focus groups, interviews, workshops etc.)	15 mins	PPT	Zoi
11:05	Break		10 mins		
11:15	Exercise on tools and methods	Identification of the best method(s) to engage with each stakeholder	45 mins	Breakout rooms. Members from 2 IOs plus 1 core team member in each group. 2 stakeholders per group to limit the discussion.	Faye, Eugenia, Sofia, Zoi

				Report back to plenary.	
12:00	Lunch Break		60 mins		
13:00	Introduction to Learning Diaries	Presentation of the template. Instructions on how to complete it.	10 mins	Template	Faye
13:10	Exercise on Learning Diaries	Scenario based on the common GA on awareness-raising regarding GBV.	40 mins	Breakout rooms. Members from 2 IOs plus 1 core team member in each group.	Faye, Eugenia, Sofia, Zoi
13:50	Conclusions and Q&A		10 mins		Core team
14:00	End				

Third Online Mutual Learning Session

September 24-25, 2024

Gender Equality in Sports Education Institutions

Objectives

The online Mutual Learning Workshop in September 2024 focuses on the following themes:

1. Collecting lessons learnt from the recent Olympics and Paralympics 2024 regarding gender equality in sports
2. Exchanging good gender equality practices in sports higher education institutions and academic departments: what difference does the sports academic environment bring to the promotion of gender equality
3. Ensuring the integration of an intersectional approach in the implementation of the institutional roadmaps and the ensuing Gender Equality Plans

Expected Outcomes

- Develop a thorough understanding of gender equality and intersectionality in sports higher education

- Discuss and be inspired by lessons learnt from the Olympics and Paralympics 2024 regarding gender equality in sports
- Share good practices in sports higher education institutions regarding gender equality
- Develop a solid understanding of the role of sports higher education in the promotion of gender equality
- Identify ways of integrating intersectionality into IOs' institutional roadmaps and ensuing GEPs

Guidelines for IOs' preparation

Prepare a 6-7 min presentation, where you will present the following topics:

1. Share an inspiring, **sports-related** practice that promotes gender equality in the sports environment. This practice should be part of one your roadmap's Grounding Actions that is really applicable to sports. If you cannot think of such an example from your roadmap, you may share a sports-related practice already existing in your institution.

2. Discuss whether and how intersectionality has been taken into account in **these activities/practices**. Are you doing anything differently since the beginning of the project/implementation of the roadmap with regard to intersectionality? If there are no intersectional inequalities addressed yet in your GAs, present how you will include intersectionality in these actions. You may draw inspiration from the Thessaloniki MLW, where we extensively discussed about intersectionality in the sports environment and you brainstormed on inequalities that intersect with gender specifically in your institution, including age (age+parenthood, age+mentality, age+management), religion, disability, socioeconomic status, nationality, physical appearance, sexuality etc.

3. Prepare two short questions to follow up your presentation in order to check the audience's understanding (e.g. in which Grounding Action / which intersectional inequality) or engage with the audience (e.g. would you do something differently? / does this apply to your institution? / have you done anything similar?).

Please prepare both the presentation and the questions and send them by 20 September EOB.

Agenda

Day I – September 24th

Time	Programme	Approach	Observations
09.00	Welcome		SEERC
09.05	Ice-breaker on impressions from the Olympics and Paralympics	Mentimeter	SEERC
09.20 – 09.50	IOC 2024 objectives and guidelines for gender equality in sports: good practices and steps forward	Presentation	SEERC
09.50 – 10.00	Break		

10.00 – 11.00	Discussion/Exercise based on the presentation		ESF, UGOT, SEERC
11.00	End of Day I		

Day II – September 25th

Time	Programme	Approach	Observations
09:00	Welcome - recap of yesterday's discussion		SEERC
09.10 - 09.20	Intersectionality: lessons learnt in Thessaloniki		ESF
09.20 – 10.50	Presentations by IOs on inspiring, sports-related practices that promotes gender equality in the sports environment (with 10-min break)	6-7 min presentations from 8 IOs (30min) Plenary discussion after 4 presentations (10 min each) 10 min break (09.55)	IOs, SEERC
10.50 – 11.00	Conclusions, Q&A and steps forward	Wrap up - Sports ecosystem, Next training session, GEP revision Upcoming actions/deadlines	SEERC

Fourth Online Mutual Learning Session

December 4-5, 2024

Zoom link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83464359535?pwd=JDRzA5eN2OZD4gZMM CtVvjCHtgWAfF.1>

Gender-based Violence in Sports and Higher Education

Objectives

The online Mutual Learning Session in December 2024 focuses on the following themes:

- Develop further the IOs' understanding of gender-based violence
- Discuss the different types of gender-based violence
- Consider gender-based violence in relation to sports, HEIs, 4I-GEPs and sustainability
- Provide IOs with the opportunity to discuss and reflect on the challenges in the implementation of Grounding Actions
- Revisit Grounding Actions in relation to gender-based violence
- Contemplate the sustainability of the roadmap actions beyond the project's lifecycle
- Actively encourage and support knowledge exchange and network expansion through participation in Communities of Practice

Expected Outcomes

- Nuanced understanding of gender-based violence and how it manifests in sports and higher education environments
- Ability to identify practical ways within their GAs to address specific GBV issues
- Understanding of sustainability principles and of the importance of ensuring a lasting impact of the roadmap activities
- Brainstorming and articulation of ideas for embedding a long-term vision of a GBV-free institution within institutional policies and practices
- Motivation to participate in Communities of Practice as a means of sustaining mutual learning and strengthening external collaborations beyond the project.

Guidelines for IOs' preparation

1. Regarding the gender-based violence exercise, please prepare to discuss the following:

- Present 1 example of gender-based violence in sports (e.g. between coaches and athletes) and 1 example of GBV in the higher education environment (e.g. among students or staff-student interactions).
- Identify the GA(s) within your roadmaps that address GBV and sexual harassment. Come up with specific actions within these GAs that could address the examples of GBV you have identified. Reflect on how you could further develop your GAs to tackle these GBV issues (e.g. including GBV in an already existing GA on awareness-raising)
- Consider the long-term steps your institution needs to take to realise your vision of a GBV-free institution.

- During the session, you will have **2 minutes to report back on what your peer IO presented**, highlighting key insights and takeaways. So make sure to **keep notes!** For inspiration and guidance, you may consult the [UNISAFE](#) toolkit.

2. During the sustainability discussion, you will work in pairs without the presence of the core team to facilitate the conversation. **Please prepare to discuss the following:**

- Select one GA from your roadmap that you wish to make sustainable.
- Share **why** you chose this particular action and discuss **how** you plan to ensure its sustainability after the project ends.
- Beyond time and financial constraints, identify any challenges or threats to the sustainability of this action.
- Ask your pair IO for their input on your sustainability plan, including good practices, potential obstacles, or new ideas to consider, and keep notes.
- You will have **2 minutes per IO to report back to the plenary on your sustainability plan** for the specific GA you have selected, the challenges you foresee, and the valuable input provided by your peer IO.

Agenda

Day I – December 4

Time	Programme	Approach	Observations
09.00	Welcome and introduction		SEERC
09.05– 09.25	Roadmap development: steps forward (actions to be taken, key deadlines, approval process from senior management-example)	Presentation	SEERC (Faye)
09.25 – 09.45	Gender-based violence (introduction to GBV, types, focus on sports and HEIs, GBV and GEPs)	Presentation	UGOT
09.45 – 09:55	Break		
09:55 – 10:35	Exercise on GBV	Breakout rooms (40 mins, IOs in pairs)	IOs, ESF, UGOT, SEERC Facilitators: Eugenia, Sofia, Faye, Zoi
10:35-10:55	Plenary	Reporting back to the plenary (2-min per IO, time-keeping)	IOs representative s report back

10.55-11.00	Highlights and recap		SEERC
11:00	End of Day I		

Day II – December 5

Time	Programme	Approach	Observations
09:00	Welcome - recap of yesterday's discussion		SEERC
09.05 –09.25	Sustainability on GEPs	Presentation	SEERC (Zoi)
09.25 – 9.50	Communities of Practice	Presentation	ESF
09.50 – 10.00	Break		
10.00 – 10.30	Discussion on sustainability	Breakout rooms 30 mins	IOs, ESF, UGOT, SEERC
10.30 - 10.50	Plenary	20 mins report to plenary (2min per IO)	IOs representatives report back
10.50 – 11.00	Highlights and conclusions	Wrap up	SEERC
11.00	End of Day II		

Fifth Online Mutual Learning Session

June 24, 2025

Zoom link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85905044957?pwd=wUUaYaM9JiUQx08VOFHhDOmxqFub69.1>

Looking Back, Moving Forward: Reflections on the SUPPORTER Journey

Objectives

As the project comes to an end, the final Mutual Learning session is dedicated to a **collective reflection on our SUPPORTER journey**, as well as an exchange of ideas on emerging topics and funding opportunities related to gender equality in sports.

This session aims to:

- Provide space for IOs and the core team to share personal and institutional reflections on the planning, implementation, and impact of SUPPORTER
- Identify key learnings and transformative experiences gained through the project at the individual level
- Explore how the project contributed to organisational change in promoting and embedding gender equality
- Initiate a conversation on post-SUPPORTER research interests and funding opportunities, to build on the project's momentum.

Guidelines for IOs' preparation

Reflect on these 2.5 years of SUPPORTER. What did you learn? How did you evolve, from academics/professionals into change agents? How did your institution evolve regarding understanding, endorsing and promoting gender equality? Was there anything you would have liked to learn from this project that you did not?

Please prepare a 4-min presentation addressing the following:

- Share one thing you learned from the project
- Share one thing you will change in your organisational practices regarding gender equality, stemming from your increased knowledge from the project?
- If you were to turn back time to SUPPORTER's first day, what would you have done differently regarding the implementation of the project activities from your end?

Agenda

Time	Programme	Approach	Observations
09.00	Welcome and introduction		SEERC
09.05– 09.55	General Assembly	Presentation	ESF

09.55 – 10.40	Reflections on the SUPPORTER project	Mentimeter Presentation	SEERC IOs
10.40 – 10.55	Break		
10:55 – 11:20	Reflecting on reflections (discussing similarities, differences, and why)	Plenary discussion	SEERC
11:20-11:45	Research after SUPPORTER: interests and funding opportunities	Presentation	SEERC, All
11.45-12.00	Conclusions		SEERC

Annex 3 – Learning Diary Templates

Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive Gender Equality Plans

Learning Diary

Document name: <e.g. Learning Diary 1, 2, 3 etc.>

Author: <Add the name of your institution>

Submission date: [DD. MM. YY]

Project acronym:	SUPPORTER
No. of Learning Diary:	<e.g. Learning Diary 1,2,3>
Submission date:	[DD. MM. YY]
Time frame covered by this Learning diary:	[DD. MM. YY – DD. MM. YY]
Person(s) responsible for the diary entry:	
Implementing Organisation's name:	
Monitoring and Mentoring Partner:	<SEERC / ESF / UGOT>
Work Package:	WP3

Introduction

The SUPPORTER Project aims to assist you in the creation of innovative, inclusive and impactful gender equality plans (4I-GEPs), adjusted to the particularities of sports higher education. To do so, Work Package 3 combines three different schemes. First, the capacity-building scheme, which consists of three training modules which offer a deep and uniform understanding of institutional change, gender+ equality in the sports education context and the development of GEPs. Second, the Mutual Learning scheme, which promotes the meaningful interaction among you as implementing organisations and the consortium as a whole, through the exchange of good practices. And third, the Monitoring and Mentoring scheme, under which the mentoring team will assist each implementing organisation individually, by providing guidance for the co-creation and implementation of the institutional roadmaps.

One of the most important tools to facilitate this mentoring process is the Learning Diary (LD). The learning diary is a record, in the form of a field book, of all the activities and reflections of each implementing organisation within a specific period. During the implementation of institutional roadmaps, each organisation will prepare *five* learning diaries in order to report on the actions planned and to collect insights on the project's activities and outcomes. These are Learning Diaries 2, 3, 4, 6 and 7, and they will be developed with the help of Template 2 found in this document.

To also ensure that the trainings offered under the capacity-building scheme are relevant and essential to you, you are invited to draft two more learning diaries with a different format. These diaries will focus on the understanding of key concepts, the existing needs and your aspirations regarding the upcoming training and mutual learning activities. These are Learning Diaries 1 and 5, and they will be developed with the help of Template 1 found in this document.

The learning diaries are not an evaluation tool, and they will not be shared with anyone outside the consortium. They are rather a self-reflection tool, for internal use only, to help you keep track of what is being done under the project, and to allow the mentoring team to better understand your needs and support you in the implementation of all the activities and grounding actions of your roadmaps.

Please prepare each learning diary using the relevant template and adding the corresponding number in the document title. Each learning diary shall be submitted to the respective WP3 folder on Microsoft SharePoint by the final submission date. Upon submission, you may inform your monitoring team and organise a bilateral mentoring and monitoring meeting with them in order to discuss advancements on the institutional roadmaps and seek guidance with respect to future activities and required actions both during and after the project period. Table 1 depicts the time plan, the area of focus of the learning diary and the respective template to be used for its drafting. Table 2 links each IO to their mentoring contact team.

Table 1

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Month</i>	<i>Final Submission date</i>	<i>Focus</i>	<i>Template</i>
Learning Diary 1	February 2024 (M11)	25/02/2024	Training Module I & II	1
Learning Diary 2	May 2024 (M14)	25/05/2024	Roadmap Implementation	2
Learning Diary 3	September 2024 (M18)	15/09/2024	Roadmap Implementation	2
Learning Diary 4	December 2024 (M21)	15/12/2024	Roadmap Implementation	2
Learning Diary 5	January 2025 (M22)	25/01/2025	Training Module III (4I-GEPs)	1
Learning Diary 6	April 2025 (M25)	25/04/2025	Roadmap Implementation	2
Learning Diary 7	July 2025 (M28)	10/07/2025	Roadmap Implementation	2

Table 2

<i>Implementing Organisation</i>	<i>Month</i>
GSTUPES	ESF (Ildi and Eugenia)
SUPES	
NSA	
UVT	
UNIBL	SEERC (Faye)
UL	
LSU	
CU	SEERC (Zoi Tatsioka)

Template 1: Learning Diary [Insert number] on the capacity-building programme

Learning outcomes from the previous training module

Understanding

Following the first cycle of trainings and mutual learnings, how do you understand and operationalise gender, gender equality, intersectionality, gender-based violence and gender equality in sports in your specific IOs context? For example, numerical versus substantive, gender bias in recruitment, equal pay, inequality grounds, forms of violence, issue of coaching, gendered fields of sport?

Description

Think through and describe how you identified the relevant stakeholders from the mapping (the core group) and how you set it up. For example, did you conduct a new stakeholder mapping and how; did you use an existing gender equality committee, nothing existed before, or something else?

Internal stakeholders' involvement in the training activities

Based on your stakeholder mapping, which stakeholders¹ are included in your core group to in designing the grounding actions to achieve your 4I-GEP?

Reflecting on good practices

Reflection on successful experiences / practices

Could you reflect on what worked well in identifying and setting up your core group? For example, do you have any positive experiences regarding intersectionality, diversity and inclusion?

Use of specific tools

Which of the introduced methods/tools for the stakeholder mapping (e.g. the “Different degree of involvement: from core to occasional members –different circles of involvement - and classification according to different level of influence and resistance”) did you find most effective and why? See presentation from the training [here](#).

¹ [D5.1 Dissemination, Engagement and Exploitation Strategy](#) entails the following non-exhaustive list of internal stakeholders: a) IOs’ internal institutional network (internal decision-makers, governance, HR, employee representatives/unions, student unions...), and b) IOs’ external networks (sports ecosystem, similar academic institutions, various sports organisations, local and national sports organisations networks, students, athletes, general public). The same document non-exhaustively refers to the following potential external stakeholders: SUPPORTER’s network at various levels: ‘sister’ and related projects, RPOs from Eastern Europe and all over Europe, policymakers, RFOs, research communities working in the gender equality field (COPs), and the general public. In the identification of internal stakeholders, you may also use the Internal Stakeholder Mapping you carried out in the framework of the online Mutual Learning Workshop in December, which launched the co-design of your roadmap.

Reflecting on challenges

Description of challenges and resistances

Did you face any challenges/difficulties in identifying and setting up your core group? For example, regarding intersectionality, inclusion and diversity.

Impact of challenges and resistances

How did these obstacles and challenges affect your setting up of the core group?

Impressions

What could/would you do to prevent or to address similar challenges/resistances?

Training needs/future steps

Description of future activities

Please describe what 4I-GEP elements/aspects (objectives, measures/actions, indicators, targets, timeline, responsibilities) you would like to gain a more advanced understanding on. Take into account the training and mutual learning programme (Deliverable D3.1 - you find it in WP1 - > T1.1 -> 2. SUPPORTER Deliverables -> D3.1) and reflect on what you and your core group need.

General Comments

Additional comments

Is there anything else that you would like to consider/suggest regarding future training activities?

Template 2: Learning Diary [Insert number] on the implementation of the institutional roadmaps

Activities in the reporting period

Description of the activities

Please describe the steps/actions that you have taken during this reporting period in relation to the implementation of your institutional roadmap.

Involvement in the activities

Which internal and external stakeholders² have you involved in order to implement your institutional roadmap?

How did you engage them?

What are the stakeholders' tasks and responsibilities?

Use of specific tools

Could you elaborate on the methods you employed to organise and carry out your actions?

(e.g. design of questionnaires/interview guides, dissemination methods or techniques to recruit participants etc.)

² [D5.1 Dissemination, Engagement and Exploitation Strategy](#) entails the following non-exhaustive list of internal stakeholders: a) IOs' internal institutional network (internal decision-makers, governance, HR, employee representatives/unions, student unions...), and b) IOs' external networks (sports ecosystem, similar academic institutions, various sports organisations, local and national sports organisations networks, students, athletes, general public). The same document non-exhaustively refers to the following potential external stakeholders: SUPPORTER's network at various levels: 'sister' and related projects, RPOs from Eastern Europe and all over Europe, policymakers, RFOs, research communities working in the gender equality field (COPs), and the general public. In the identification of internal stakeholders, you may also use the Internal Stakeholder Mapping you carried out in the framework of the online Mutual Learning Workshop in December, which launched the co-design of your roadmap.

Table 3: Schematic representation of implemented activities

Type of activity	Relevant GA	Date	Location	Involved stakeholders	Main objective	Employed tools

Best practices

Description of Successful Experiences / Accomplishments

Could you describe any good practices/ successful experiences within the reporting period?

Note: This could be in reference to both the implementation of the institutional roadmap and the other activities of the SUPPORTER project (e.g. mutual learning programme).

2. Impressions

Have these activities you carried out during this reporting period satisfied the success criteria you have established for your institutional roadmap?

Have you been able to reach the targeted stakeholder groups?

Challenges

Description of Challenges and Obstacles

Did you face any challenges/difficulties in achieving the reporting period's goals? (e.g. difficulty in organising activities/recruiting participants, difficulty in obtaining necessary resources etc.)

How did you tackle these obstacles and challenges?

Note: This could be in reference to both the implementation of the institutional roadmap and the other activities of the SUPPORTER project (e.g. mutual learning programme).

Impact of Challenges and Obstacles

How did these obstacles and challenges affect the results of your initiative or action?

Impressions Why do you think the specific obstacles emerged? What kind of actions could be attempted in the future to not only tackle obstacles, but to prevent them altogether?

Future steps

Description of Future Activities Please briefly describe your plans for the upcoming reporting period (events, meetings, other types of activities). Would you need any help (discussions/suggestions) from other partners in this project to carry out your planned activities?

General Comments

Additional comments

Is there anything else that you would like to report regarding your activities during this reporting period?

**Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with
Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive
Gender Equality Plans**

Learning Diary

Document name: Learning Diary 5

Author: <Add the name of your institution>

Submission date: [DD. MM. YY]

Project acronym:	SUPPORTER
No. of Learning Diary:	Learning Diary 5
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NSA	
UVT	
UNIBL	SEERC (Faye)
UL	
LSU	
CU	SEERC (Zoi Tatsioka)

Learning Diary 5 on the capacity-building programme

Learning outcomes from the project so far: Focus recommendations

1. What would be your main recommendation to a a) Faculty of Sport and b) National Sports Organisation wishing to develop a 4I GEP in terms of:

- Building a strong foundation for promoting GE, or in other words: in order to be able to develop a robust, well-founded GEP?

2. What would be your main recommendation to a a) Faculty of Sport and b) National Sports Organisation wishing to develop a 4I GEP in terms of:

- Contributing to structural change for gender equality

3. What would be your main recommendation to a a) Faculty of Sport and b) National Sports Organisation wishing to develop a 4I GEP in terms of:

- Addressing intersectionality in the context of sport which operates in inequality silos?

4. What would be your main recommendation to a) a Faculty of Sport and b) a National Sports Organisation wishing to develop a 4I GEP in terms of:

- Conditions (formal and informal) for recognising that gender-based violence is an issue to be addressed by the institution.

Training needs/future steps

5. Description of future activities

Please describe what 4I-GEP elements/aspects (objectives, measures/actions, indicators, targets, timeline, responsibilities) you would like to gain a more advanced understanding on.

General Comments

6. Additional comments

Is there anything else that you would like to consider/suggest regarding future training and mutual learning activities?

**Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with
Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive
Gender Equality Plans**

Learning Diary

Learning Diary 6

Author: <Add the name of your institution>

Submission date: [DD. MM. YY]

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Introduction

The SUPPORTER Project aims to assist you in the creation of innovative, inclusive, intersectional and impactful gender equality plans (4I-GEPs), adjusted to the particularities of sports higher education. To do so, Work Package 3 combines three different schemes. First, the capacity-building scheme, which consists of three training modules which offer a deep and uniform understanding of institutional change, gender+ equality in the sports education context and the development of GEPs. Second, the Mutual Learning scheme, which promotes the meaningful interaction among you as implementing organisations and the consortium as a whole, through the exchange of good practices. And third, the Monitoring and Mentoring scheme, under which the mentoring team will assist each implementing organisation individually, by providing guidance for the co-creation and implementation of the institutional roadmaps.

One of the most important tools to facilitate this mentoring process is the Learning Diary (LD). The learning diary is a record, in the form of a field book, of all the activities and reflections of each implementing organisation within a specific period. During the implementation of institutional roadmaps, each organisation will prepare *five* learning diaries in order to report on the actions planned and to collect insights on the project's activities and outcomes. These are Learning Diaries 2, 3, 4, 6 and 7, and they will be developed with the help of Template 2 found here.

To also ensure that the trainings offered under the capacity-building scheme are relevant and essential to you, you are invited to draft two more learning diaries with a different format. These diaries will focus on the understanding of key concepts, the existing needs and your aspirations regarding the upcoming training and mutual learning activities. These are Learning Diaries 1 and 5, and they will be developed with the help of Template 1 found in this document.

Amendment of Learning Diary Plan

The initial plan involved the creation of two Learning Diary Templates, destined to assist the collection of reflections on roadmap activities and on identified training needs, respectively. Nevertheless, new needs emerged during the project implementation related to the development of policy recommendations, a holistic reflection on the actions carried out as part of the institutional roadmap and a self-assessment of the new 4I-GEPs by the IOs. In response to these needs, three new Templates were drafted to underpin the development of three of the Learning Diaries as follows:

- **Template 3** to develop Learning Diary 5 on reflections to inform policy recommendations
- **Template 4** to develop Learning Diary 6 on an overview of the roadmap implementation
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The learning diaries are not an evaluation tool, and they will not be shared with anyone outside the consortium. They are rather a self-reflection tool, for internal use only, to help you keep track of what is being done under the project, and to allow the mentoring team to better understand your needs and support you in the implementation of all the activities and grounding actions of your roadmaps.

Please prepare each learning diary using the relevant template and adding the corresponding number in the document title. Each learning diary shall be submitted to the respective WP3 folder on Microsoft SharePoint by the final submission date. Upon submission, you may inform your monitoring team and organise a bilateral mentoring and monitoring meeting with them in order to discuss advancements on the institutional roadmaps and seek guidance with respect to future activities and required actions both during and after the project period. Table 1 depicts the time plan, the area of focus of the learning diary and the respective template to be used for its drafting. Table 2 links each IO to their mentoring contact team

Table 1

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Learning Diary 4	December 2024 (M21)	15/12/2024	Roadmap Implementation	2
Learning Diary 5	January 2025 (M22)	25/01/2025	Policy recommendations	3
Learning Diary 6	May 2025 (M25)	2/05/2025	Roadmap Implementation	4
Learning Diary 7	July 2025 (M28)	10/07/2025	Roadmap Implementation	5

Table 2

Implementing Organisation	Month
GSTUPES	ESF (Despoina)
SUPES	
NSA	
UVT	
UNIBL	SEERC (Faye)
UL	
LSU	
CU	SEERC (Zoi Tatsioka)

Template 6: Learning Diary 6 on the overview of the institutional roadmap implementation

As you are reaching the final stages of your institutional roadmaps, it is important to create a structured repository of all your reflections from this process. This reflective exercise will capture key learnings and experiences that have laid the groundwork for the next phase in your institution's journey toward gender equality, marked by the development of your new 4I-GEPs.

The following template is structured according to the type of each Grounding Action in your roadmap (e.g. Awareness-Raising, Research and Education, Establishing New Bodies/Procedures, Data Collection). It is thus designed to support you in collecting information on all the Grounding Actions implemented, along with the related activities, and it invites you to reflect on internal and external evaluations, based on the success criteria you defined during the co-creation phase.

For each activity you report, please indicate which Grounding Action it corresponds to. You are encouraged to draw on your previous Learning Diaries, where some of this information may already have been recorded.

Important note: If your roadmaps do not include Grounding Actions on some of the following topics, please ignore the corresponding tables.

AWARENESS-RAISING AND TRAINING GROUNDING ACTIONS

List of the activities

Please list all events you organised under your awareness-raising Grounding Actions.

Relevant GA	Type of event [e.g. seminar, lecture, workshop, social media campaign]	Title of event	Participant profile	Date and Location	Duration

Brief description of the events

Provide a short summary for **each** of the events listed above, including:

- **Topics** discussed
- Type of speakers/facilitators (no names, just roles – e.g. academics, HR staff, senior management)
- **External engagement:** Involvement of **external** stakeholders (as participants, consultants, presenters)
- **Key takeaways** from the event

Note 1: Please complete a separate summary for each event.

Note 2: If your Grounding Action involved an awareness-raising campaign, also describe how the campaign was disseminated (through emails, internal newsletters, posters on notice boards, class announcements, social media and press releases – using posters, infographics etc.)

Evaluation of the events

Present the evaluation results for each event, based on participants’ feedback and any pre- and post-survey tools used

Note: Include this information in the form of tables or figures – no need to attach the full survey text.

Self-assessment / Lessons learnt

Share **one key lesson** from each awareness-raising Grounding Action you implemented.

Example: From the two events under GA1 on awareness-raising, we learnt that the presence of senior management as advocates for institutional gender equality initiatives significantly increased staff engagement and encouraged open dialogue among participants.

DATA COLLECTION GROUNDING ACTIONS

Overview of activities

List all gender-related data collection activities conducted under these GAs.

Relevant GA	Type of data collected <i>[e.g. gender-disaggregated statistics, perception surveys, qualitative gender audits]</i>	Target groups	Tools and methods

Brief description

Please provide a short description of this process, including:

- **What kind** of data was collected (e.g. % of females in leadership positions, reports of GBV cases, etc.)
- **Who** was involved in the collection and analysis of the data
- **Whether and how** the collected data supported other GAs or procedural changes
- Whether and how **an intersectional approach** was embedded in this process

Key findings

Outline only the **most important findings** that emerged from your data collection, such as:

- Any trends, gaps, or inequalities identified
- Anything unexpected or noteworthy findings that would be relevant to share with the consortium

Self-assessment / Lessons learnt

Share **one key lesson** from the data collection process, such as:

- A limitation or a challenge encountered during the data collection process (e.g. low participation)
- A good practice you would recommend or plan to embed in your new GEP

Example: The survey on gender-based violence attracted very few student participants. In the future, we need to communicate its purpose and importance more effectively, and ensure the student council is actively involved in the dissemination process.

GROUNDING ACTIONS ESTABLISHING OR UPDATING INSTITUTIONAL POLICIES

Overview of policies developed or updated			
Please list all institutional policies that were developed or revised under these GAs.			
Relevant GA	Title of the policy	Objective	Status [e.g. draft/formally approved/pending approval]
Summary of each policy			
For each of the policies listed above, provide a short summary including:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whether it is newly developed policy or an update of an existing one • The main areas or themes it addresses • Who was involved in its development • The intended target group(s) 			
Dissemination and Reception			
Briefly describe how the policy (or policies) were disseminated across the institution.			
Share how the policy was received by relevant stakeholders, reflecting on any resistances or questions raised and positive responses at management, staff and student level.			
Self-assessment / Lessons learnt			
Include one key lesson you gained from the process of developing or updating institutional policies.			
<i>Example: The approval process took significantly longer than expected due to unclear internal procedures. In the future, we will involve legal and administrative units earlier in the process to ensure more timely approval.</i>			

GROUNDING ACTIONS ON DEVELOPING NEW PROCEDURES, STRUCTURES OR BODIES

Overview of procedures and internal structures developed

Please list any new procedures, internal structures, or institutional systems developed as part of your institutional roadmap.

Relevant GA	Name of new procedure/ structure [e.g. GEP Committee, Confidential Help System, GBV Ombudspersons etc.]	Function/ Purpose	Status [e.g. in place, pilot phase, members recruited, mandate signed, pending approval etc.]

Brief description of the new structures/procedures/bodies

For each of the procedure or structure listed above, provide a **short** description including:

- Who was involved in its development
- Whether there was external consultation
- Its mandate, including roles and responsibilities
- Any training provided to new body members
- Whether and how it was communicated to relevant institutional stakeholders

Self-assessment / Lessons learnt

Share **one key lesson** from the process of developing or implementing these procedures or structures.

Example: We initially proposed appointing a student as one of the confidential contact persons for the GBV Help System. However, this was not permitted under our institution's current regulations, so we had to revise our plan. In future efforts, we will consult institutional rules more thoroughly before designing new roles.

RESEARCH AND EDUCATION GROUNDING ACTIONS

Overview of procedures and internal structures developed

Please list the key modules/research topics where gender has been integrated.

Relevant GA	Type of activity [e.g. curriculum revision, new modules, new research topics]	Module name / Research topic	Embedded GE - related topics

<p>Brief description and evaluation</p> <p>For each of the activity listed above, provide a short description including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who was involved in the process • The approach used (e.g. the academic board discussed the curriculum update and revisions to course materials, guidelines for gender-sensitive methodologies) • Whether gender was integrated into mandatory or elective courses / research topics • Results of any feedback collected by staff, students or researchers 			
<p>Self-assessment / Lessons learnt</p> <p>Share one key lesson from the process of embedding gender into research or education.</p> <p><i>Example: We introduced a short module on gender bias in research design as part of a doctoral training programme. However, we realised it was not sports-oriented, so we plan to update and tailor it to the sports environment.</i></p>			

COMMENTS

Please add a brief description of any activities carried out within your institutional roadmap that were not included in the above tables. Remember to mention the relevant GA.

Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive Gender Equality Plans

Learning Diary 7

Document name: <e.g. Learning Diary 1, 2, 3 etc.>

Author: <Add the name of your institution>

Submission date: [DD. MM. YY]

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Key components of our new GEP

Intersectionality

An intersectional GEP considers gender in relation to its intersections with other sociocultural, economic and political inequalities such as race, ethnicity, class, sexuality, age, dis/ability, nationality and so on, and proposes actions which take into account how different forms of inequality and disadvantage interconnect.

Check the boxes that apply to what you have included in your GEP in terms of intersectionality, and explain how (in 1-2 sentences max):

- Multiple and overlapping inequalities were considered in the data collection process
- Measures are taken to support underrepresented groups of different genders
- The GEP promotes diverse representation in decision-making (e.g. consultation/members from various ethnic, disability, socioeconomic backgrounds etc.)?
- The modules which address GE aspects integrate an intersectional perspective
- Other:

Impact

An impactful GEP entails a growing institutional capacity of the organisation for gender mainstreaming along a number of pre-identified intermediate stages and themes for change. Twelve key themes have been identified: core team of change agents; capacity/skills of the change agents for driving institutional change for gender equality; leadership actively committed to gender equality/gender mainstreaming; availability of resources; data collection and statistical analysis; involvement of internal stakeholders; involvement of external stakeholders and experts; coverage of the different dimensions/areas of gender equality; Institutional change; transparency and accountability; institutional policy-making based on robust understanding of gender equality; organisational culture; and organisational governance.

Check the boxes that apply to what you have included in your GEP in terms of impact, and explain how (in 1-2 sentences max):

- Each GEP objective is linked to specific measures and actions

- GEP measures are linked to specific targets and indicators (outputs, outcomes, impacts)
- The GEP Committee is adequately trained
- External stakeholders and experts were involved in the GEP development process
- A dissemination and communication strategy has been designed
- Other:

Inclusiveness

GEPs should address inclusiveness in its design, implementation, and evaluation in the following forms: 1) inequalities and inclusivity by considering other sociocultural factors in relation to gender+ such as race, ethnicity, age, sexuality, disability etc.; 2) geographical inclusiveness by recognising the local and regional differences between organisations and enabling knowledge transfer from more advanced to less experienced organisations; 3) internal inclusiveness by engaging internal stakeholders ranging from students, administrative and academic staff to top management; and 4) intersectoral inclusiveness by engaging external stakeholders.

Check the boxes that apply to what you have included in your GEP in terms of inclusiveness, and explain how (in 1-2 sentences max):

- A diverse range of stakeholders have been engaged in its development and in the implementation plan?
- Are your policies and actions accessible to all (disability-friendly, language-inclusive)?
- Do your measures foster an open and safe culture for all genders?
- Other:

Innovation

An innovative GEP entails the implementation of measures that demonstrate originality and creativity in fostering gender equality. This may involve introducing new ideas, concepts, and intersections; employing advanced participatory methods; forming unconventional partnerships; or implementing targeted actions to address emerging challenges. In other words, an innovative GEP offers out-of-the-box solutions to address common GE issues, while being inclusive, intersectional and impactful.

Check the boxes that apply to what you have included in your GEP in terms of **innovation, and explain how (in 1-2 sentences max):**

- Is your GEP innovative in terms of concepts, methods, and partnerships?
- Have you introduced new methods, tools, or participatory approaches regarding GE?
- Does your plan challenge traditional gender equality frameworks?
- Are you integrating best practices from other institutions or sectors?
- Other:

Embedding measures against gender-based violence

Check the boxes that apply to what you have included in your GEP in terms of **GBV, and explain how (in 1-2 sentences max):**

- Does your new GEP examine the prevalence of all forms of gender-based violence in your institution?
- Does your new GEP have organisational policies in place to combat gender-based violence?
- Does your new GEP have a protocol for reporting and investigating GBV cases?
- Does your new GEP include measures for the support of gender-based violence victims?
- Does your new GEP foresee regular trainings and awareness-raising activities to help create a culture of zero tolerance for gender-based violence?
- Are the reporting mechanisms ensuring protection of victims from retaliation (e.g. failing marks in a module etc.)?
- Other:

Tailored to the sports environment

Check the boxes that apply to what you have included in your GEP in terms of **sports-specific measures**, and explain (in 1-2 sentences max):

- Does the curriculum include discussion on gender stereotypes in sports, leadership and media representation?

- Are students, coaches and staff educated on gender bias in sports through trainings, coursework and awareness-raising activities?

- Are gender stereotypes in the portrayal of athletes/coaches addressed?

- Are gender stereotypes in sports participation explained and addressed?

- Does your new GEP include measures to increase women's representation in coaching and sports management roles?

- Other:

